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A new surgical approach for open cholecystectomy: Our experience

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Abstract

Background: Gallstone disease is the most common of all abdominal diseases for which patients are admitted to hospital in developed countries. Various surgical approaches have been described for the surgical removal of the gall bladder including the Cokher subcostal incisions which divide all layers of the abdominal wall, the right paramedian incision, the middle incision, the right upper transrectal incision (no longer used), the mini-laparotomy incision cutting all layers, and the laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Each of these approaches has its advantages, disadvantages, and complications

Patients and methods: During six months period from February 1999 to August 1999, we performed cholecystectomy on 50 patients with symptomatic gall stones (43 females, 7 males) at Gulpgani Hospital of Qum Iran using a new surgical approach. 17 patients had associated problems; 6 had associated common bile duct stones, 3 had diabetes, 3 had hypertension, 3 were obese weighing over 100 kilograms, and 2 patients each had mitral stenosis and chronic bronchitis. The new approach making a small 4-5 cm incision cutting only the skin and fascia without cutting muscles or nerves aiming at reducing the surgical complications of the traditional

approaches such as significant postoperative pain, atelectasis, incisional hernia. Also to shorten the time of anesthesia and to reduce blood loss and hospital stay with achieving early mobilization.

Results: No significant complications such as wound infection or hematoma were observed during the postoperative period. All patients were followed for 3 months without the occurrence of any complications.

Conclusion: We recommend the use of this approach when laparoscopic cholecystectomy is not convenient.

Keywords: Cholecystectomy, New approach, Complication

Introduction

Gallstone disease is the most common of all abdominal diseases for which patients are admitted to hospital in developed countries [1] and an increase in hospital admission rates was registered in the 1990s [2] The prevalence of gallstone increases with age [3]. Hence, the safety and cost-effectiveness of treatment of gallstone disease in populations with increasing age is of great importance to public health. Cholecystectomy is the treatment of choice. The common bile duct may be cleared of gallstones at

cholecystectomy or through endoscopic sphincterotomy, which involves an extra procedure [4]. Length of hospital stay for cholecystectomy became shorter during the 1980s [5,6]. and it was demonstrated that open cholecystectomy could be performed through a smaller incision than the traditionally used [7]. Small-incision or mini-laparotomy cholecystectomy was found compatible with ambulatory surgery (3 – 10 hrs postoperative hospital stay) [8].

However, laparoscopic cholecystectomy rapidly became the preferred technique in the early 1990s [9]. Population-based studies demonstrated great variations in cholecystectomy rates between countries before the introduction of the laparoscopic technique [5]. Thereafter, cholecystectomy rates increased in Scandinavia [10] Scotland [6], UK [3] and in the US [11]. At the end of the 1990s 70–80% of all cholecystectomies were completed as laparoscopic procedures [6,12,13]., which then had also been found compatible with ambulatory surgery [14,15]. The shift from open to laparoscopic cholecystectomy has been accompanied by an increased incidence of iatrogenic bile duct injury [16] and an increase in the overall incidence of intra-operative injury [17].

Patients and methods

During six months period from February 1999 to August 1999, we performed cholecystectomy on 50 patients with symptomatic gall stones (43 females, 7 males) at Gulpigani Hospital of Qum, Iran using a new surgical approach. 17 patients had associated problems; 6 had associated common bile ducts stones, 3 had diabetes, 3 had hypertension, 3 were obese weighing over 100 kilograms, and

2 patients each had mitral stenosis and chronic bronchitis. Routine pre and postoperative preparations included ultrasound, CXR, complete blood count, blood sugar, BUN and serum creatinine, PT, PTT, and LFTs. The new approach making a small 4-5 cm incision cutting only the skin and fascia without cutting muscles or nerves aiming at reducing the surgical complications of the traditional approaches such as significant postoperative pain, atelectasis, incisional hernia. Also to shorten the time of anesthesia and to reduce blood loss and hospital stay with achieving early mobilization.

1-We performed small surgical incision directly over the gall bladder area at the junction of the lateral rectus abdominous muscle.

2-After the skin and facial incisions, we retracted the rectus muscle medially after undermining the facial flaps.

3-We splitted the internal oblique muscle with direction of fibers as in the grid iron incision.

4-The peritoneum was opened directly over the gall bladder fundus.

5-Gall bladder removed ante-or retro - gradely according to its state.

Results

No significant complications such as wound infection or hematoma were observed during the postoperative priod. 43 patients experienced entirely smooth postoperative period, received oral fluids within 24 hours, and were discharged within 24-48 hours. 6 with associated common bile ducts stones and common bile ducts exploration stenosis and one patient with chronic bronchitis complicated by atelectasis were discharged 5 days later. 7 patients required single 50 mg of pethidine to

relieve mild postoperative pain. All patients were followed for 3 months without the occurrence of any complications

Discussion

Cholecystectomy is a commonly performed procedure in patients with symptomatic cholelithiasis. With an estimated incidence up to 2.17 per thousand inhabitants [18, 19], and 500,000 cholecystectomies performed annually in the USA [20] and 21,000 in The Netherlands (an incidence of 1.31 per thousand inhabitants) [21,22], gallstones are a major cause of morbidity in the Western world.

Various surgical approaches have been described for the surgical removal of the gall bladder including the Cokher subcostal incision which divide all layers of the abdominal wall ,the right paramedian incision ,the middle incision, the right upper transrectal incision (No longer used),the mini-laparotomy incision cutting all layers ,and the laparoscopic cholecystectomy [5, 8, 12, 13].Each of these approaches has its advantages, disadvantages ,and complications such as postoperative pain, hematoma, infection, atelectasis, subcostal parasthesia ,and incisional hernia.

During the 1980s, the preferred surgical technique for cholecystectomy changed from the classical open procedure to a smaller incision approach [23, 24] and eventually to laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Although evidence of superiority was never delivered, the laparoscopic technique was accepted as the gold-standard procedure by consensus [20].

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is the most performed and acknowledged minimally invasive operation in The

Netherlands (15,000 laparoscopic cholecystectomy procedures in 2005) [26-28]. Still, a regular complication of this procedure remains iatrogenic biliary tract injury [26, 29, 30]. The most common cause of serious injuries is misidentification of the anatomy in general and misidentification of the cystic duct in particular [26, 30-35].

Conclusion: We recommend the use of this approach when laparoscopic cholecystectomy is not convenient.

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Spinal traction in lumbosacral disc prolapse

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Abstract

Background: Lumbosacral disc prolapse is a common cause of low back pain localized to the lumbar spine. The aim of this paper is to describe the possible role of lumbar spine traction in the therapy of lumbosacral spine disc prolapse.

Patients and methods: 866 patients were treated with lumbar traction in and 150 patients were treated with analgesic and non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), both groups had lumbosacral spine disc prolapse .The traction was used for not more than 2weeks.

Results: 72% of patients gained 100% response at week 2, 17% showed partial response and 11 % showed poor response.

Conclusion: The results of this trial indicate that use of lumbar traction in lumbosacral disc prolapse is probably better than analgesic and NSAIDs.

Keywords: Lumbosacral spine disc, prolapse, Low back pain, Traction.

Introduction

Back pain is the most common problem world wide; it is the most frequent cause of disability in people under 45years.The term low back pain in this study will be used to describe the symptom complex in which the pain is localized to the

lumbar spin and due to the lumbosacral disc prolapse. Most attacks of back pain are self limiting and of short duration. However, persistent pain may need additional therapy .The five lumbar vertebrae are linked by intervertebral disc anteriorly [1-5] Pain which is a subjective symptom is the cardinal feature of lumbar disc protrusion[6,7,8].Lumbar disc disease is the most frequent major pathology seen in back pain clinics [9,10,11] A prolapsed intervertebral disc may present with severe and crippling sciatica of acute onset or as recurrent dull back pain of many years duration, the signs may vary from minimal limitation of spinal movement to an almost immobile spine accompanied by gross neurological changes in legs [12,13] Neurological signs are due to the physical involvement of the spinal cord or its nerve roots by disc prolapse [14].Compression , tension or angulations of a nerve root will cause symptoms and recurrent trauma may well give rise to edema of nerve roots [15,16,17].

The essential physical sign of disc prolapse is limitation of spinal movement with constituent limitation of straight leg raising and unilateral or bilateral leg pain. Back pain may occur without sciatic radiation although both are usually present. Pressure from the

disc protrusion is directed posteriorly, posterolaterally or laterally [18, 19]. Intermittent lumbar traction is an active technique which theoretically attempts to reduce the size of the intervertebral protrusion. There are various forms of equipment designed to exert traction on the lumbar spine while patients lie on specially designed traction table [20, 21].

Patients and methods

966 patients, 742 were males and 224 were females. Their age ranges from 18-52 years with a mean of 39 years. They had been followed in the rheumatology clinic during a period of 4 years. Clinically all patients gave a history of chronic low back pain (pain persisted more than 12 weeks). Some patients were complaining of severe unremitting back pain but most of them had a constant and nagging pain that radiated into buttocks and legs and was punctuated by periods of acute exacerbation. 696 patients (72 %) of the total number of patients gave a history of heavy weight lifting before the development of low back pain while 270 patients 28% did not remember any performance which might have led to their back pain.

Conventional radiographs of the lumbosacral spine had been done which showed evidence of loss of disc spaces in all patients with loss of normal lordosis of the spine.

The diagnosis of lumbar disc prolapse was done on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) examination for all patients. The disc prolapse localized to L4/L5 in 36% of patients (319 patients) while 299 patients (31%) showed multiple level disc prolapse.

The control group composed of 150 subjects randomly chosen 84 males and 66 females, all of them complaining of

low back pain due to lumbar disc prolapse for more than 12 weeks proved by MRI.

All patients received intermittent traction usually applied for 20-30 minutes every other day with heat therapy to the lumbar region (short waves or micro waves) in order to relax muscles the weight used from 25-40 Kg, the weight applied by special equipment designed to exert traction on the lumbar spine while patients lie on specifically designed traction table.

The traction continues with re-examination after each 6 sessions until the pain relief has been achieved.

The control group was treated with analgesic plus diclofenac 50mg two times daily, regular examination every two weeks for the control group. For all patients in both groups traction was maintained for a period not exceeding 2 weeks depending upon the improvement of the back pain.

The student t test was used to compare the degree of response among different groups of patients, A (P) value of <0.05 was designated statistically significant.

Results

966 patients received skeletal traction (lumbar) 30-40Kg for 10-20 minutes every other day for two weeks for each patient. The onset of response was rapid in those patients after traction with an increase in response rate after each sessions of traction.

A complete response (100% disappearance of pain) was observed in 35 % (338 patients) in the first week and 72 % (699 patients) at week two.

In patients who received traction there was significant [$P < 0.01$] reduction in back pain after two weeks of skeletal

traction in comparison with the other group of patients which was composed of 150 patients who did not show any significant improvement on analgesic and non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs).

The remaining patients 17% (164 patients) showed partial response noticed by the patients themselves. They noticed decrease in the severity of pain, stiffness and improvement in the mobility of the person. Only 11% (106 patients) treated with traction thought that the improvement was poor.

The control group 150 patients who did not respond to analgesic with NSAIDs after two weeks they received traction on the same principles of group one they showed excellent improvement. In disappearance of pain only 7% (11 patients) showed poor improvement. No complications appeared during the procedure of lumbar traction.

Discussion

Low back pain remains a common challenging symptom of lumbar disc prolapse causing loss of working hours in the community especially in those who had chronic problem with unremitting disease 15. The results in this study suggest that lumbar traction every other day is highly effective and extremely safe in the management of lumbar disc prolapse and it is superior to analgesic and non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). Through out follow up patients assigned for lumbar traction showed greater therapeutic benefit than other therapies. Many of the patients who participated in the trial had failed other treatment.

Patients thought previously to be

refractory to therapy who refused to undergo surgical intervention had an additional therapeutic option, lumbar traction was well tolerated.

Conclusion: The beneficial outcomes from lumbar traction have clinically important implications. Traction has been shown to provide a rapid onset of benefit.

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Measurement of bilirubin in the newborns by bilirubinometer

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Abstract

Objective: High blood concentrations of bilirubin are toxic to the brain and may cause kernicterus. Therefore, determination of bilirubin levels is performed for many newborns, and several different methods are available. We compared 2 standards used for bilirubin determination among newborns under routine conditions, to define their sequence of use.

Methods: This study was carried out during the period from March 2003 and December 2006 at the Vaccine and Sera institute / Ministry of Health, Baghdad, Iraq. Bilirubin concentrations were determined with 2 standards: local standard (prepared from chemical compound which has a broad spectral absorption peak at 460 nm, this solution is stable indefinitely), and randox standard (obtained industrially by extraction of either cattle or pig bile, or bovine, and it can be isolated as light-sensitive orange-red crystals with certain "stability" about 24 hours).

Results: A total of 100 samples were obtained. The 2 standards showed very strong correlations (correlation coefficients 0.9999) with each other; and; their means were used as comparison values. In the routine care of newborns, the measurement of total bilirubin by bilirubinometer provides better agreement with local standard

than does randox and it is the first choice. Testing specimens based on human serum would provide meaningful information regarding the accuracy and precision of total bilirubin assays. The ability to grade proficiency testing participants for accuracy, using target values determined by the reference method, could become a valuable contribution toward improving the quality of bilirubin assays, which is essential for the management of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia

Conclusion: Local standard give accurate information on bilirubin concentrations as do randox standard did, and presented the best results.

Keywords: Hyperbilirubinemia, Newborn, Measurement

Introduction

Jaundice is a common condition among neonates, caused by the combination of increased heme catabolism and physiologic immaturity of the liver in bilirubin conjugation and excretion [1]. For most healthy term newborns, unconjugated bilirubin levels increase above 170 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (10 mg/dL) between the third and sixth days of life and decrease in the following days. Greater and more prolonged increases in bilirubin levels can be caused by hemolytic disorders, birth trauma [2] Clinically relevant hyperbilirubinemia is also seen among breastfed or premature

newborns [3,4]. High concentrations of bilirubin are toxic to the brain and may cause a specific type of bilirubin-related encephalopathy called kernicterus. Therefore, determination of bilirubin levels is performed for many newborns. The device used for this purpose is the bilirubinometer. Investigations for accuracy in bilirubin measurements have been conducted. In addition, routine laboratory methods for the determination of serum TB levels differ markedly [5, 6]. On the basis of these studies, it is difficult to decide which result is used to determine bilirubin levels and, more importantly, how to interpret the results obtained. As a consequence, therefore, we prepared a new standard and compared it with randox standard for determination bilirubin for newborns, under routine conditions.

Methods

The study was conducted during the period between March 2003 and December 2006 at the Vaccine and Sera Institute/, Baghdad, Iraqi Ministry of Health. For each newborn, bilirubin concentrations were determined with 2 different standards, local and randox.

Preparation of new bilirubin standard

Commercially available bilirubin standard is randox calibrator solutions obtained industrially by extraction of either cattle or pig bile, or bovine, and it can be isolated as light-sensitive orange-red crystals (Randox laboratories ltd, diamond road, crumlin, co, antrim, United Kingdom). However, there is always a risk of infection from this material. Our new standard equivalent to 16mg/dl is prepared from Potassium chromate which has a broad spectral absorption peak at 460 nm, similar to bilirubin, this solution is stable

indefinitely [7, 8]. The molar extinction coefficient for local standards at 460 nm is 46,400, similar to molar extinction coefficient for randox standard, measures the absorbance and constructs a calibration graph by plotting the bilirubin concentrations against the corresponding absorbance values. The calibration graph plotted against absorbance values is as shown in Figure-1. Graph I, The measurable range with this graph is from 3 to 273 μ mol/l. Once linearity is proved. A standard is set up every time that patient's samples are analyzed.

Method Comparison

A total of 100 samples were obtained from infants. The mean age at the time of blood sampling was 3 days (range: 0–8 days). The samples were collected into heparin-containing, after heel puncture (9, 10). Plasma was separated and immediately assayed for bilirubin for clinical purposes. Samples were used to measure bilirubin concentrations by bilirubinometer (bil-read) (11, 12). The instrument measures the bilirubin concentration in 20 μ L of plasma without dilution. Calibration was performed with the use of a local and randox standard. And the reportable range was 0.0–513.0 μ mol/L (0.0–30.0 mg/dL). The time required for bilirubin analysis with this instrument was 15 s.

Analytical Performance
to investigate accuracy, quality controls were used from randox (certified reference material). Quality controls were performed at 3 different levels (30, 150, and 300 $\mu\text{mol/L}$). These quality controls were also used to assess within-run imprecision and day-to-day imprecision. Linearity assessments were performed with duplicate measurements for samples.

Statistical Analyses
Data were analyzed with Microsoft Excel 2000, with Passing-Bablok regression analyses, Bland-Altman plots.

Results

A total of 100 samples were obtained from infants. The mean age at the time of blood sampling was 3 days (range: 0–8 days). Plasma bilirubin concentrations for these patients were between 9 and 388 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. The median slope of the regression lines from the 50 study days was 1.090 (range, 1.010–1.180), and the median y -intercept was 0.2 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (range, 3.1 to 12.3 $\mu\text{mol/L}$). Regression lines were extremely linear with a median goodness of fit (r^2) of 0.9999 (range, 0.9996–1.0000). The intraassay CVs ($n = 20$) were 1.5%, 1.0%, and 1.2% and the interassay CVs ($n = 50$) were 4.3%, 2.5%, and 1.3% for 30, 150, and 300 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, respectively. In the patient samples, total bilirubin concentrations were 13.8–410 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ when measured with conventional method (randox), compared with 14.4–400 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ when measured by new standard.

Figure. 2A shows regression analysis according to Deming (1.002 (95% confidence interval, 0.914–1.090) and a y -intercept of -3 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (95% confidence interval, -20 to 12

$\mu\text{mol/L}$). The correlation coefficient (r^2) was 0.85 ($P < 0.001$).

Discussion

Determination of TB levels is one of the most frequently performed laboratory tests for neonates. In this study; we used 2 different standards for calibration bilirubinometer that measures bilirubin levels. According to information provided by the proficiency material manufacturer, all reference standards were bovine albumin in origin, with certain "stability" about 24 hours only at (2 – 8) c, and may have transmissible pathogenic agents, and it is expensive, but our standard is chemical substance, has highest purity, stability indefinitely at (2 – 8) c, not hygroscopic, readily available and not expensive. Results comparison for 2 standard used in our study showed extremely strong correlations with each other, and having the best agreement.

Conclusion: Local standards gave accurate information on bilirubin concentrations as do randox standard did, and presented the best results. Their readings can be trusted up to 388 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Due to economical and low risk infective reasons, they can be considered as first choice.

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Figure (2): Correlation between total bilirubin concentrations measured in plasma by (radox Ref standard) and those measured by (new standard). (A), regression according to Deming. The dashed line represents the line of identity. (B), Bland–Altman difference plot. Mean difference (solid line) \pm 2 SD (dashed lines) is shown.

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Testicular size and resistive index measured by gray scale and color Doppler ultrasound before and after varicocelectomy in adult patients with unilateral idiopathic varicocele

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Abstract

Background: Varicocele represents abnormal dilatation and tortuosity of the veins of the pampiniform plexus within the spermatic cord, caused by incompetent valves in the internal spermatic vein. The small vessels of the pampiniform plexus normally range from 0.5-1.5 mm in diameter. As varicocele cause dilatation of these vessels, their diameters usually exceed 2 mm. To evaluate testicular volume and resistive index (RI) of the intra-testicular artery as an indicator of improved seminal parameters after surgical treatment in adult patients with idiopathic varicocele.

Patients and methods: This prospective study was done in the ultrasound unit of AL-Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital from the period of November 2006 to July 2008 including the follow up. Forty one patients with left sided idiopathic varicocele (mean age: 27 years; range: 19–40 years), underwent unilateral varicocelectomy were included in the study. Testicular size, RI and seminal parameters were measured before and one year after surgery.

Results: All patients had evidence of reversed flow (venous reflux) and are classified as: 30 patients (73.2%) had grade III and the remaining 11 patients

(26.8%) had grade II reflux. In terms of seminal parameters, all the patients had abnormal sperm count.

Statistical analysis showed a significant increase of testicular volume after varicocele treatment (pre operative 16.55 ± 2.22 ml, post-operative 18.46 ± 2.05 ml) ($P < 0.05$). A statistically significant decrease in RI values of intratesticular arteries after varicocelectomy was also shown (pre operative 0.74 ± 0.08 , post-operative 0.59 ± 0.06) ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, the total number of spermatozoa and fast progressive spermatozoa rates significantly increased after surgery (respectively $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.01$).

Conclusion: Varicocele repair results in increased testicular volume and improved semen profiles. The intratesticular RI seems to be a reliable indicator for routine clinical use to identify subfertile men. Ultrasound is useful to monitor the presence of varicocele, to assess recurrence of varicocele and to evaluate testicular function.

Keywords: Testicular size, Resistive index, Color doppler US, Varicocelectomy, Idiopathic varicocele.

Introduction

Anatomy: The testicular arteries arise from the anterior aspect of the aorta just below the level of the renal arteries. They enter the spermatic cord at the internal inguinal ring. At the posterosuperior aspect of the testis, the testicular artery divides into branches that pierce tunica albuginea (capsular arteries) which supply centripetal branches that enter the testicular parenchyma. Venous drainage occurs via a plexus of veins called the pampiniform plexus, which lies above and behind the testis and build one vein at the upper end of the inguinal canal. The right vein drains into the inferior vena cava while the left vein drain into the left renal vein [1, 2.]

Varicocele: Varicocele represents abnormal dilatation and tortuosity of the veins of the pampiniform plexus within the spermatic cord, caused by incompetent valves in the internal spermatic vein [3]. The small vessels of the pampiniform plexus normally range from 0.5-1.5 mm in diameter. As these vessels dilate in varicocele, their diameters increased and usually exceed 2 mm [4].

The rate of clinical varicocele ranges from 9% to 23%, but this increases to 40% in infertile patients. Most cases of varicocele are idiopathic; they are found mainly in adolescents and young adults and rarely develop after the age of 40[4-7].

The idiopathic varicocele occurs when the valves within the veins along the spermatic cord don't work properly. This results in backflow of blood into the pampiniform plexus and causing increased pressures, ultimately leading to damage to the testicular tissue, 98% of

idiopathic varicoceles occur on the left side, apparently because the left testicular vein runs vertically up to the renal vein, while the right testicular vein drains directly into the vena cava. A secondary varicocele is due to the compression of the venous drainage of the testicle, pelvic or abdominal malignancy is a definite concern [4].

Varicocele is normally diagnosed by physical examination through palpation of the spermatic cord before and during Valsalva maneuver with the patient in a standing position. They are typically identified as a painless compressible mass, often referred to as "a bag of worms. Vascular lesions have been arbitrarily divided into 3 grades based up on physical findings: large varicoceles are visible; medium varicoceles are palpable; and small varicoceles are only palpable during a Valsalva maneuver. Varicoceles detected by radiological imaging studies in patients without a palpable varicocele are labeled subclinical [8, 9].

Varicocele can be reliably diagnosed with ultrasound, as they appear as multiple hypoechoic serpiginous and tubular structures of varying sizes, predominantly >2 mm in diameter and located superior and lateral to the testis [3, 10, 11].

The resistive index (RI) is derived from an arterial Doppler spectrum which reflects the arterial impedance. The assessment of the testicular RI is widely used to measure intratesticular blood flow [12-16].

The aim of this study was to evaluate changes in testicular volume and resistive index of the intra-testicular artery as an indicator of improved seminal parameters after surgical

treatment in adult patients with idiopathic varicocele.

Patients and methods

This prospective study was done on 41 patients with left sided idiopathic varicocele (mean age: 27 years; range: 19–40 years). The study was done in the ultrasound unit of Al-Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital during the period of November 2006 to July 2008 including the follow up. All patients had a history of infertility. All patients underwent preoperative physical examination to assess if the varicocele is palpable.

Scrotal U/S was performed with a high-resolution sonography system (Sonoline Versa pro, Siemens Medical System) using a 7-10 MHz linear array transducer. The examination protocol included the preoperative evaluation of the varicocele with gray scale, color and pulsed wave Doppler U/S (to assess the degree of venous reflux) and the evaluations of the size of the testis. The length, width, and anteroposterior diameter of the testes were measured (each diameter is measured 3 times and the mean value was calculated). Testicular volume was calculated using the following formula: $\text{Volume} = \text{Length} \times \text{Width} \times \text{Depth} \times 0.52$.

The RI was measured three times in each testicle at an intratesticular artery in the upper, middle and lower testicular pole, and the mean value was calculated.

Sonography was performed at a mean follow-up of 1 year after surgery. None of the patients had recurrence of their varicocele during this follow-up period. Postoperative measurements included testicular volume, colored and pulsed wave Doppler and measurement of the RI at an average time of 1 year after the procedure.

The seminal parameters were examined before and at an average time of 1 year after surgery. All semen samples were collected after a period of 3 days of abstinence.

Statistical analysis using the program SPSS (version 15 for Microsoft Windows). The testicular volume, RI and seminal parameters were compared before and after surgery. Statistical significance was indicated by a p value of less than 0.05. The testicular volume and RI measurements, number of spermatozoa and fast progressive spermatozoa before and after surgery were expressed as mean \pm SD.

Figure-1 shows Gray scale ultrasound of varicocele seen as echo-free serpiginous structures. Figure-2 shows Color Doppler US of the testis transverse view shows centripetal artery (curved arrow) in red and small adjacent vein (straight arrow) in blue. Figure-3 shows color Doppler sonogram shows response of varicocele to Valsalva maneuver. A: without Valsalva. B: with Valsalva shows an increase in diameter with reversed flow within the varicocele

Figure (1): Gray scale ultrasound of varicocele seen as echo-free serpiginous structures.

Figure (.2): Color Doppler US of the testis transverse view shows centripetal artery (curved arrow) in red and small adjacent vein (straight arrow) in blue.

Figure (.3): color Doppler sonogram shows response of varicocele to Valsalva maneuver. A: without Valsalva. B: with Valsalva shows increase in diameter with reversed flow within the varicocele

Results

All the 41 patients examined and included in this study have clinical diagnosis of left sided varicocele and presented with infertility. On ultrasound those patients had vein diameter equal or > 3 mm.

On color and pulsed wave Doppler ultrasound all patients had evidence of reversed flow (venous reflux) and were classified as: 30 patients (73.2%) having grade III whereas the remaining 11 patients (26.8%) had grade II reflux (table 1).

In terms of seminal parameters all the patients had abnormal sperm count. Statistical analysis showed a significant increase of testicular volume after varicocele treatment (pre operative 16.55± 2.22 ml, post-operative 18.46± 2.05 ml) (P < 0.05) (table 2).

A statistically significant decrease in RI values of intratesticular arteries was recorded after varicocelelectomy. The preoperative RI value was 0.74± 0.08 (mean ± SD) compared with 0.59± 0.06 post-operatively (p < 0.001) (table 2).

Furthermore, the total number of spermatozoa and fast progressive spermatozoa rates significantly increased after surgery (respectively P < 0.05 and P < 0.01) (table 2).

The Spearman correlation coefficient showed a good relationship between testicular volume, RI and total number of spermatozoa (r = 0.445; P = 0.01).

There is no statistical correlation between age and testicular volume or seminal parameters before and after treatment.

	No. of patients	%
Grade II	11	26.8
Grade III	30	73.2
Total	41	100%

Table 1: number and percentage of varicocele according to grade of venous reflux

Discussion

Many reports have demonstrated the correlation between varicocele and infertility, and the literature published over the past 40 years has shown that both sperm parameters and pregnancy rates improve in varicocele patients after treatment [6, 17].

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	P value	Total
Testicular volume	Pre operative	16.55	2.22	14.00	22.70	P < 0.05	41
	Post operative	18.46	2.05	15.50	23.90		41
No. of spermatozoa (million/ml)	Pre operative	38.5	28.4	4	80	P < 0.05	41
	Post operative	48.3	28.8	5	80		41
Fast progressive spermatozoa (%)	Pre operative	9.5	10.2	5	45	P < 0.01	41
	Post operative	20	17.4	6	60		41
Resistive index	Pre operative	0.74	0.08	0.56	0.94	P < 0.01	41
	Post operative	0.59	0.06	0.47	0.69		41

Table 2: means, standard deviation, minimum & maximum values and P value of testicular volume, number of spermatozoa, fast progressive spermatozoa & resistive index in pre and post operative state

Varicocele is often accompanied by testicular growth arrest and reduced volume [12, 18-20]. Both testicular consistency and seminal parameters deteriorate over time when varicoceles are not repaired [21, 22].

Venous reflux and testicular temperature elevation appear to play important role in varicocele-induced testicular dysfunction [23].

Numerous studies have demonstrated that there is a clear an increase in testicular size in adolescent subjects following surgical repair as a resumed growth of the testicle [24, 25, 26–30].

Unquestionably, the problem is more widely debated with regard to adult subjects, as the theory that correction of varicocele means improved fertility has not been universally accepted. The wide variability of the data reported in the literature is mainly due to the lack of randomized long term studies and to the evaluation of different parameters, such as seminal parameters or pregnancy rate. Furthermore, the major part of current literature does not value testicular volume or testicular growth but only fertility improvements.

The vast majority of physicians who manage male infertility patients believe that varicoceles are a major cause of male infertility and that repair of a varicocele will improve fertility [31]. Adult varicocelectomy is an important therapeutic modality used in the treatment of male infertility [32]. The American Urology Association and the Practice Committee of the American Society of Reproductive Medicine (ASRM) currently recommend that treatment should be offered only when varicoceles are palpable [33]. However Cornud et al (1999) noted that treatment of subclinical varicoceles with grade 3 reflux resulted in changes similar to those seen after repair of palpable varicoceles [14].

In the first part of our study we evaluated the effect of varicocelectomy on testicular size and its impact on spermatogenesis. A statistically significant increase in testicular volume is seen after varicocele treatment (P < 0.05). Furthermore, the total number of spermatozoa and fast progressive spermatozoa rates also significantly increased after surgery (respectively P <

0.05 and $P < 0.01$). These results are compatible with those reported in previous studies [30, 34-38]. This can be explained by the fact that the removal of varicocele restores the normal testicular temperature and results subsequently in increased sperm production [39].

In adult subjects, the increase of a mean of about 1 cm³ in the size of the testicle at the 1-year follow-up simply confirms the undeniable utility of the surgical treatment. Moreover, it can clearly be noted that an increase in testicular volume corresponds to an increase of approximately 50% in the number of spermatozoa produced and double the fast progressive spermatozoa rate.

In the second part of our study, we evaluated the effect of a varicocelectomy on RI. The assessment of the testicular RI is widely used to measure intratesticular blood flow [16]. Spectral Doppler sonography is a good method for identifying flow in the testes, with use of the time-velocity spectrum to quantify blood flow [40]. Capsular and intratesticular waveforms consistently show a low-impedance pattern [1], with a mean RI value of 0.62 (range, 0.48-0.75). Increased RI of capsular branches of testicular arteries on spectral Doppler examination may be an indicator of impaired testicular microcirculation in patients with clinical varicocele [41]. However subclinical varicocele does not seem to affect the intratesticular arterial RI [42].

In our study, a high-resistance flow was present preoperatively in the testis with the varicocele, but after varicocelectomy a statistically significant decrease in RI values of intratesticular arteries was shown ($p < 0.001$). This indicates that the postoperative flow showed a low resistance. The preoperative increase in RI in patients with varicocele could be explained by the increasing impedance

to the venous or lymphatic outflow caused by the venous reflux and venous stasis due to the incompetent valves, which in turn may result in an increase of the RI.

When the valves within the veins along the spermatic cord don't work properly, this results in backflow of blood into the pampiniform plexus and causes increased pressures, ultimately leading to damage to the testicular tissue [4]. Our result supports this explanation as after varicocelectomy the RI decreased significantly. This decrease in RI may reflect the vasodilatation and increased blood flow [23-25]. Our result is equivalent to that reported by Pinqera GM, et al indicating that a RI of >0.6 might be suggestive of a pathological sperm count [43].

Conclusion: 1. Varicocele repair in adults with a clinical left varicocele increased left testicular volume and improved semen profiles.

2. The intratesticular RI as measured by CDUS seems to be a reliable indicator for routine clinical use to identify subfertile men.

3. Ultrasound imaging performed during the follow-up of treated patients not only makes it possible to monitor the presence of recurrent varicocele, but is also extremely helpful for the evaluation of testicular function.

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MRI findings in patients with neurogenic claudication suspected to have central lumbar spinal stenosis

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Abstract

Background: Central lumbar spinal stenosis (CLSS) presents as neurogenic claudication. CLSS can also be found radiologically in asymptomatic patients. The major aim of this study was to comprehensively analyze MRI-findings in patients with neurogenic claudication.

Patients and methods: MRI of 64 consecutive patients [average age of 63.5 ± 14 year (Mean \pm SD), 34 patients (53 %) were female] with suspected spinal claudication was included in this retrospective analysis. CLSS was considered to be present whenever dural sac had an AP-diameter < 10 mm and cross-sectional area ≤ 70 mm². According to the dural sac cross-sectional area a classification of severity of CLSS was proposed.

Results: CLSS was found in 21 patients (32.8 %). Patients with CLSS were older than those with no CLSS (mean 70 versus 63 year; $p = 0.02$). No correlation was observed between the occurrence of spinal stenosis and the patient's gender (57 % were female; $p = 0.65$). Almost half of patients referred by orthopaedic

surgeons showed to have CLSS compared with 17 % of patients referred by other physicians ($p = 0.02$). No correlation was found between the severity of spinal stenosis and the patient's age and gender, level of stenosis and the referring physicians ($p = 0.956$, 0.179 , 0.310 , and 0.491 respectively).

Degenerative spondylolisthesis and Modic changes type I was encountered more frequently in patients with CLSS but the difference was statistically non-significant. Sciatica occurs equally in patients with CLSS and in patients with disc extrusion compared with patients whose MRI did not show CLSS or disc extrusion.

Conclusion: Patients with neurogenic claudication should undergo MRI. MRI enables measurement of the cross-sectional area of dural sac, classification of severity of CLSS and may help the physician to plan suitable treatment. The referring physician should be aware of other problems that mimic spinal stenosis.

Keywords: MRI, Spinal stenosis, Cross-sectional area, Dural sac.

Introduction

Central lumbar spinal stenosis (CLSS) is defined as narrowing of the spinal canal to an extent that result in compression of cauda equina and the lumbar/lumbosacral nerve roots [1]. CLSS is usually caused by congenital narrowing, acquired narrowing or both. Patients with congenital spinal stenosis are characterized by having short and thick pedicles. Acquired CLSS in adults was originally described by Verbiest [2–4]. Acquired CLSS is the far most common type of spinal stenosis and is often degenerative. As patients grow older, the biomechanical failure of the degenerated discs increases the stress on facet joints and ligamentous attachments, resulting in their hypertrophy. Bone thickens and osteophytes build at the facet joints as a result of chronic stress or repeated minor trauma [5]. A loss of disc height result in reduction of the interlaminar space which subsequently results in narrowing the spinal canal as the dorsal edge of the upper lamina overrides the rostral edge of the lower lamina. Posterior protrusion of the disc contributes to stenosis and nerve root entrapment in the midline, lateral recesses, and neural foramen [6]. Hypertrophy of ligamenta flava contributes also to the development of CLSS.

Patients with CLSS presents with neurogenic claudication which is defined as complaints of leg pain when walking a certain distance. Neurogenic claudication is exacerbated by standing erect and by downhill ambulation and is relieved by lying supine more than prone, sitting, squatting, and by lumbar flexion [7]. Pain on standing and pain relieve on sitting showed to have specificity for CLSS of 93% and a sensitivity of 46% [8]. Neurogenic

claudication need to be distinguished from vascular claudication as their treatment is quite different. Neurogenic claudication is not exacerbated with biking or uphill ambulation [7]. Pain diminution with sitting (80 % pain reduction) and with forward bending (75% pain reduction) were reported by Getty et al [9] and is believed to support the diagnosis of neurogenic claudication and spinal stenosis.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT) and CT-myelography have improved the ability to establish a correct diagnosis in patients with neurogenic claudication, to localize the level of spinal canal compromise and to study the impact on lateral recess and neural foramen. MRI has the advantage of not exposing the patients to ionizing radiation. Compared to CT, MRI can more accurately show the soft tissue changes contributing to the CLSS. Some disadvantages of MRI are longer examination time, less availability and higher cost. These imaging techniques enable also distinguishing CLSS from disc extrusion as a cause of patient's symptom as the treatment strategy is quite different. CLSS is often treated with decompressive laminectomy, often combined with medial facetectomy or with foraminotomy in cases of associated stenosis of lateral recess and/or neural foramen. In cases of segmental instability the latter operations should be combined with fusion (instrumented or non-instrumented). However radiological evidence of CLSS in asymptomatic patients has been reported in up to 20 % of adults examined with MRI or CT [10].

Based on the above facts the aim of this study was to thoroughly study the MRI findings in patients with neurogenic claudication, to define the

prevalence of CLSS in these patients and to find out if the orthopaedic surgeons had a higher diagnostic accuracy than other referring physicians. The other aims of the study were to explore the correlation between the occurrence of CLSS and the degree of severity of CLSS with different predictors such as patient's age and gender, referring physicians and the level of stenosis.

Patients and methods

All lumbar MRIs performed in our radiology department during one year period (2008) were retrospectively subjected to a computerized search in the picture archiving and communication systems (PACS). This search identified 361 patients who underwent lumbar MRI with suspicion of degenerative diseases. CLSS was the clinical question at issue in 67 patients (18.5 %). The medical records of these patients were scrutinized to exclude malignancy or recent trauma. A total of 64 consecutive patients (17.7 % of all patients with suspected degenerative disease) with spinal claudication and suspicion of CLSS were included in this retrospective analysis. Thirty four patients (53 %) were female. The average age of the patients included in the analysis was 63.5 ± 14 year (Mean \pm SD), median age of 66 year and the range of 27–78 year. All patients were examined in one of the 3 MR-scanners at our institution with a field strength of 1.5 Tesla (Avanto, Sonata or Symphony; SiemensAG, Medical Solutions, Erlangen, Germany). The same imaging protocol was used in all patients: 3-plane localizer, sagittal T1-weighted images (T1WI), sagittal T2-weighted images (T2WI), axial T1WI and axial short-tau inversion-recovery (STIR) images. In patients with sciatica or radiculopathy a coronal T1WI was added. All

examinations were assessed in PACS which enabled measurements of the sagittal diameter and the cross-sectional area of the dural sac. All images were assessed in consensus fashion by two neuroradiologists. Criteria for CLSS were: (1) sagittal diameter of dural sac < 10 mm, and (2) cross sectional area of dural sac ≤ 70 mm² measured on axial images obtained parallel to disc plane. We have proposed the following classification of the severity of CLSS: (1) moderate CLSS when the dural sac has been reduced to a cross-sectional area of 60–70 mm², (2) relatively severe CLSS when the dural sac has been reduced to a cross-sectional area of 40–59 mm², and (3) severe CLSS when the dural sac has been reduced to a cross-sectional area < 40 mm².

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed by means of SPSS (originally, Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). To compare the occurrence of CLSS in patients referred by orthopaedic surgeons and those referred by other physicians, SPSS automatically computes Fisher's exact test in addition to chi-square test when the table has a cell with an expected frequency of less than 5. Statistical significance was set to P value ≤ 0.05 . In the same way the occurrence of sciatica/radiculopathy, disc extrusion, degenerative spondylolisthesis and Modic changes Typ-1 in patients with CLSS was compared with that in patients whose MRI did not show CLSS. Independent samples t-tests were performed to test the correlation between severity of CLSS and the gender. Pearson correlation was performed to explore the correlation between the severity of CLSS, patient's age and level of the pathology. Non-parametric analysis (Mann Whitney test) was performed to find out if there was

any correlation between the occurrence of spinal stenosis and the patient's age as well as the correlation between the cross-sectional area of the dural sac and the patient's gender, level of pathology and the type of referring physician.

Results

Spinal stenosis:

In 64 patients with neurogenic claudication included in analysis of this study, MRI was totally normal in five patients (7.8 %) and showed CLSS in 21 patients (32.8 %). Other abnormalities were observed in the remaining 38 patients (59.4 %). Patients with CLSS were slightly older than those whose MRI did not show CLSS with mean age of 70 ± 11 year (Mean \pm SD) compared with 63 ± 15 year (Mann Whitney test, $p=0.022$), Figure 1.

Figure 1: Age distribution among patients with spinal stenosis (1) and those with no spinal stenosis (0).

Twelve out of 21 patients with CLSS were female and 9 were male ($p=0.65$). CLSS was found at 33 levels as 8 patients (38 % of patients with CLSS)

had CLSS at two different levels and 2 patients (10 % of patients with CLSS) had CLSS at three different levels. The most common level affected by CLSS was L4-L5 followed by L3-L4 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of CLSS and disk degeneration at different disc levels.

Of 64 patients with neurogenic claudication, 35 (55 %) were referred to the radiology department by orthopedic surgeon of whom 16 patients (46 %) showed to have CLSS compared with 5 out of 29 patients (17 %) referred by other physicians. This difference was statistically significant (Fisher's exact test; $p=0.02$), Table 1. In the whole study cohort 25 patients (39 %) suffered from sciatica/radiculopathy beside neurogenic claudication. Among patients with CLSS 11 patients (52 %) suffered from sciatica compared with 14 patients (33 %) whose MRI did not show CLSS. This difference was statistically non-significant (Fisher's exact test; $p=0.13$), Table 1. The occurrence of degenerative spondylolisthesis was more common among patients with CLSS (29 % compared with 12 % in patients with no CLSS). However this difference was statistically non-significant (Fisher's exact test; $p=0.07$), Table 1. Modic changes type I i.e. degenerative bone

marrow edema in two adjacent endplates encountered more frequently in patients with CLSS (24 % compared with 16 % in patients with no CLSS). This difference was not statistically significant (Fisher's exact test; p=0.51), Table 1.

	Referring physicians		P-value
	Orthopedic surgeons	Other physicians	
Spinal stenosis	16 (46 %)	5 (17 %)	0.02
No spinal stenosis	19 (54%)	24 (83 %)	
sciatica			
	Yes	No	0.13
Spinal stenosis	11 (52 %)	10 (48 %)	
No spinal stenosis	14 (33 %)	29 (67 %)	
Disc degeneration			
	Yes	No	0.89
Spinal stenosis	14 (67 %)	7 (33 %)	
No spinal stenosis	28 (65 %)	15 (35 %)	
Disc extrusion			
	Yes	No	0.04
Spinal stenosis	2 (10 %)	19 (90 %)	
No spinal stenosis	14 (33 %)	29 (67 %)	
Degenerative spondylolisthesis			
	Yes	No	0.07
Spinal stenosis	6 (29 %)	15 (71 %)	
No spinal stenosis	4 (12 %)	30 (88 %)	
Modic changes Typ1			
	Yes	No	0.51
Spinal stenosis	5 (24 %)	16 (76 %)	
No spinal stenosis	7 (16 %)	36 (84 %)	

Table 1: The results of Fisher's exact and chi-square test in testing the association between spinal stenosis and different possible predictors.

CLSS was moderate in 15 levels out of 33 (46 %), relatively severe in 13 levels (39 %) and severe in 5 levels (15 %). Pearson correlation test showed no statistically significant association between the severity of CLSS and patient's age and level of the pathology (p= 0.956 and 0.310 respectively). At all 33 levels of CLSS identified in our study the AP-diameter of dural sac was < 10 mm. This was also the case in cases classified as moderate CLSS (n=15) [p <0.001].

Non-parametric analysis (Mann Whitney test) showed no correlation between cross-sectional area of the dural sac (and consequently the severity of CLSS) and the patient's gender, level of pathology and the type of referring physician (p= 0.179, 0.172 and 0.491 respectively).

Other MRI findings:

Disc degeneration was found in 42 patients (65.6 % of study cohort) and constitutes the most common finding in MRI of this study cohort. As 23 of 42 patients showed degeneration at more than one level, disc degeneration was found at totally 99 disc levels with frequencies increasing in caudal direction (Figure 2). Disc levels L4-L5 and L5-S1 were almost equally affected (25 and 26 discs respectively). Disc degeneration occur almost equally in patients with CLSS and in patients whose MRI did not show CLSS (67 % and 65 % respectively) which make the difference statistically non-significant (Fisher's exact test; p=0.89), Table 1.

Disc extrusion (disc herniation) in patients with neurogenic claudication whose MRI did not show CLSS was the second most common finding (n= 16, 25 %). Other MRI-findings are shown in Table 2. Only two patients (10 %) with CLSS had disc extrusion compared with 14 patients (33 %) whose MRI did not

show spinal stenosis. This difference was statistically significant (Fisher's exact test; $p=0.04$), Table 1.

Findings	Number
Disc degeneration	99 levels
Disc extrusion (disc herniation)	16
Modic changes type II-III	14
Modic changes type I	12
Degenerative spondylolisthesis	10
Schmorl's noduli without edema	8
Spondylolytic spondylolisthesis	6
Schmorl's noduli with edema	4
Vertebral compression	4
Osteonecrosis	2
Synovial cyst	1
Meningioma	1

Table 2: MRI findings other than spinal stenosis.

Sciatica was the most common associated symptom with neurogenic claudication but the occurrence of sciatica was not statistically significant neither in patients with disc extrusion nor in patients with spondylolisthesis compared with those whose MRI did not show any of these abnormalities. Half of patients with spondylolisthesis did not complain of sciatica (Fisher's exact test; $p= 0.30$) and 56 % of patients with disc extrusion had no sciatica (Fisher's exact test; $p=0.57$).

Regarding causes of CLSS, 13 patients had the typical combination of hypertrophy of facet joints, thickened ligamenta flava, osteophytes and bulging discs. In seven patients they had the above combinations in addition to another cause: Two patients had congenital canal stenosis, two patients had disc extrusion, two patients had canal compromise due to old vertebral compression, and one patient had congenital canal stenosis and epidural lipomatosis as additional causes.

Figure 3 (A-E) MRI images of different patients with spinal stenosis. (A) Sagittal T2WI of a patient with relatively severe CLSS at the level of L4-L5 with reduced sagittal diameter of the dural sac. (B) Sagittal T1WI of another patient with very severe CLSS at the level of L4-L5 with markedly reduced sagittal diameter of the dural sac (black arrows shows the anterior and the posterior limits of the dural sac). CLSS is caused by disc protrusion and degenerative spondylolisthesis (white arrow). (C) Axial STIR-image of a patient with moderate CLSS. Dural sac cross sectional area was estimated to 60 mm². (D) Axial T1WI of a fourth patient with neurogenic claudication shows a relatively severe CLSS with dural sac cross sectional area of 45 mm². (E-F) axial T1WI and STIR-image of a patient with very sever CLSS at the level of L4-L5. Dural sac was reduced to a cross sectional area of 30 mm². Note marked hypertrophy of fact joints (black arrows, E) and thickened ligamenta flava (white arrows, E).

One patient had epidural lipomatosis as the only cause of CLSS. Figure 3(A-F) shows example of different patients with CLSS with different degree of severity.

Discussion

As the radiological evidence of CLSS can be encountered in patients with no symptoms of CLSS [10–11], our study included only patients referred to the department of radiology due to symptoms of neurogenic claudication. As the degree of constriction of the spinal canal necessary to cause symptoms of spinal stenosis is not well defined, the definition of spinal stenosis remains unclear. Verbiest et al [3] identified two groups on myelography: absolute spinal stenosis (AP-diameter ≤ 10 mm) and relative spinal stenosis (AP-diameter 10–12 mm). Sortland et al [12] described improved myelographic techniques with flexion-extension provocation and defined an AP-diameter of 10.5 mm in extension as the lower normal limit.

With regard to definition of spinal stenosis in term of reduction of dural sac cross-sectional area there are no well defined limits. Previous studies have reported a good correlation between the anteroposterior (AP) diameter of the dural sac and the cross-sectional area of the dural sac evaluated by computed tomographic investigation [13–14]. Results of studies on human cauda equina have reported an increase in the pressure among the nerve roots when the dural sac was reduced to a cross-sectional area of $< 75\text{--}80$ mm² [15], which approximately correspond to an AP-diameter of 5–8 mm. These critical measurements of dural sac area showed to vary at different spinal levels: 76.9 mm²/11.4 mm (cross sectional area/sagittal diameter of dural sac) at L2

,71.5 mm²/11.1 mm at L3 and 64.8 mm²/10.6 mm, at the L4 [15]. Schonstrom et al [16] have shown that spinal compressive loading from weight bearing reduces spinal canal dimensions. Based on the above information and the fact that evaluation of images nowadays in PACS enables easy measurement of cross sectional-area of dural sac, we have thus proposed the classification of the degree of spinal stenosis as described in “material and methods”. This classification enabled grading the severity of CLSS that can help planning the treatment and predicting the prognosis as it has been shown that patients with severe CLSS benefit more from decompressive surgery [17]. However normal cross sectional area of dural sac on MRI performed in supine position does not reflect the status of the dural sac during axial loading. Dynamic MRI-studies of lumbar spine with axial loading has been recommended by some studies in patients with sciatica or neurogenic claudication when the dural sac cross-sectional area at any disc location estimated to be < 130 mm² [18]. As expected the most common level affected by CLSS was L4-L5 because of maximal mobility at this disc level compared with L5-S1 level where the mobility is usually restricted by the ilio-lumbar ligaments. Our study has also shown that the occurrence of spinal stenosis has a poor correlation with the different predictors studied. The finding of spinal stenosis in only $\frac{1}{3}$ of this study cohort which only include symptomatic patients highlights the need to perform some radiological examination before deciding the type of treatment, preferably MRI. Other MRI findings (Table 2) such as disc extrusion, spondylolisthesis etc should be analysed thoroughly by the referring orthopaedic surgeon to whether they explain the

patient's symptoms. At the same time the physician should be familiar with other causes of symptoms that mimic neurogenic claudication (Table 3) as this might necessitate another radiological or laboratory modalities to reach the final diagnosis that explain the patient's symptom and can direct them to the proper treatment. One explanation to why the diagnostic accuracy of the orthopaedic surgeons was higher than that of other physicians is that the orthopaedic department in our hospital is a tertiary referral unit to which the patients with highly suspected spinal stenosis are referred in comparison to e.g. family doctors who usually have all possible varieties of patients with back pain.

Hip osteoarthritis.
 Vascular claudication (peripheral vascular diseases).
 Trochanteric bursitis.
 Spondylolisthesis.
 Spondylodiscitis and epidural abscess.
 Seronegative spondyloarthropathies such as ankylosing spondylitis, Reiters syndrome and Crohn's spondyloarthropathy.
 Diffuse idiopathic skeletal hyperostosis.
 Peripheral neuropathy.
 Trauma especially in elderly with osteoporosis.
 Scoliosis.

Table 3: List on differential diagnosis of spinal stenosis

Conclusion

Our study has shown that orthopaedic surgeons have a better diagnostic accuracy as almost half of patients they referred showed spinal stenosis compared with 17 % of patients referred by other physicians. No correlation was found between the occurrence of spinal stenosis and the patient's gender. There was a statistically significant difference with regard to patient's age. No correlation between the severity of spinal

stenosis and the patient's age and gender, level of stenosis and the referring physicians was observed. This study has shown that sciatica or radiculopathy occur equally in patients with CLSS and in patients with disc extrusion compared with patients whose MRI did not show CLSS or disc extrusion. This means that sciatica/radiculopathy is not a relevant clinical marker to whether patients with neurogenic claudication have CLSS or disc extrusion. Therefore patients with neurogenic claudication should undergo a radiological investigation, preferably MRI. The evaluation of MRI in picture archiving and communication systems (PACS) enables measurement of cross-sectional area of dural sac and classification of the severity of CLSS and thus helping the treating physician planning the suitable treatment.

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Congenital gastro-intestinal obstruction in the maternity and child teaching hospital of Al-Qadisiya

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Abstract

Background: Gastro-intestinal obstruction is probably the most common reason for emergency operation in neonates, infants and children.

Patients and methods: From July 2004 to the end of June 2007 200 ;138 male (69%)and 62 female (31%) cases of gastro-intestinal obstruction needed surgical treatment at The Maternity and Child Teaching Hospital ,Al-Qadisiya-Al-Diwaniya. Male: Female ratio2.2:1 (138:62)

Results: Vomiting was the leading sign and symptom in 133 of cases (66.4%), failure to pass meconium in 98 of cases (49%). The radiological study was the usual diagnostic aid whether conventional plain radiography used in 163 of cases (81.5%) or a contrast study. Ano-rectal obstruction caused by imperforated anus was found in 89 of cases (44.5%). 31(15.5%) had a gastric outlet obstruction, 26 (13%) had jejuno-ileal atresia, 18 (9%) had a Hirschsprung's disease, while duodenal obstruction was found in 9 cases (4.5 %.) The surgical procedures were enterostomies in 97 of cases (48.5%), intestinal anastomosis (18.7), pyloromyotomies, 30 (15%), posterior-lateral thoracotomy and esophageal anastomosis in 6(3%) and explorative laparotomy, 5 (2.5 %).

Conclusion: Ano-rectal obstruction was the commonest cause of congenital gastro-intestinal obstruction in this series. Enterostomies were the most commonly performed operations.

Keywords: Congenital, Gastro-intestinal obstruction, Pattern, Iraq

Introduction

Most surgical conditions occur as isolated findings in pediatric age group whose families have no history of similar problems. Gastrointestinal obstruction is probably the most common reason for emergency operation in neonates, infants and children. Most obstructions result from complications of congenital anomalies or inflammatory conditions that affect the digestive tube. Neonates, infants and children with such surgical problem require special consideration because of the profound physical, physiological and psychological differences, which are age-related. Pediatric surgery has been rightly termed as "the whole of surgery applied to a special age group". The aims of this study is to describe the pattern of congenital intestinal obstruction in a specific pediatric surgical unit, that of The Maternity and

Child Teaching Hospital of Al-Qadisiya-Al-Diwaniya.

Patients and Methods

From July 2004 to the end of June 2007 200 cases [138 male (69%)and 62 female (31%)] of gastro-intestinal obstruction needed surgical treatment at The Maternity and Child Teaching Hospital,Al-Qadisiya-Al-Diwaniya.

Male: Female ratio2.2:1 (138:62)All cases were evaluated by a full history and clinical examination, laboratory assessment, radiological examination, ultrasound study, echocardiogram and other studies as appropriate to confirm and gives a better evaluation and diagnosis of the pathology or other associated anomalies.

Appropriate management of each case was done .Dehydration and electrolyte imbalance was corrected and nasogastric tube was inserted, prophylactic broad-spectrum antibiotics were given preoperatively and blood was prepared prior to surgery.

Results

Table (1) shows the age of presentation of the obstruction. Table (2) shows the weight and maturity of patients studied. From the survey and the follow-up of the full gynecological and obstetrical history The history was of abortion of value in about 36 (18%) cases. Polyhydramnios was found in 35 (17.5%) of cases. Table 3 shows the patients characteristics related to the parent status. Table 4 shows maternal risk categories associated with congenital intestinal obstruction.

Vomiting was the leading symptom and can be considered as an alarming sign

Age of presentation	No. of cases	%
< 28 days	134	67
1-2month	40	20
>2-6 month	11	5.5
>2month-2 year	18	4
>2-5 year	3	1.5
>5 year	74	2
Total	200	100%

Table (1): Age of presentation

Case			Sex			
Maturity	No.	%	Male		Female	
Term	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Term	181	90.5	126	63	55	27.5
Full term	134	67	98		36	
LBW	11	5.5	6		5	
SFGA	36	18	22		14	
Premature	19	9.5	12	6	7	3.5
PSGA	9	4.5	6		3	
PAGA	10	5	6		4	

Table (2) shows the weight and maturity of patients studied

PSGA=premature small for gestational age.

LBW= low birth weight.

PAGA= premature appropriate for gestational age.

SFGA= small for gestational age.

Status	No. of cases	% from total cases
Close relative	72	36%
Relative	60	30%
Not relative	68	34%

Table (3): The patients characteristics related to the parent status.

for such pathology. 133 (66.5%) patients presented with such a complain, bilious vomiting must draw more attention for the problem. [Bilious vomiting with or without abdominal distention, is an initial sign of intestinal obstruction in newborns. Failure to pass meconium was the second leading symptom and

Risk categories		No	%	Risk categories			No.	%
1	Obstetrics history	.						
a	Abortions			3	Congenital anomalies			
	Previous history	31	15.5	A	Mother			
	Threatened	5	2.5		CHD	4	2	
b	Polyhydramnios	35	7.5		Hirschsprung's disease	1	0.5	
c	Previous dead baby	12	6		Annular pancreas	1	0.5	
e	Twins	2	1		Pyloric stenosis	1	0.5	
f	Premature labour	2	1		Renal anomalies	2	1	
g	Hyper-emesis gravidarum	1	0.5		Imperforate anus	1	0.5	
				B	Family			
	Ovarian tumor	1	0.5		hydrocephaly	2	1	
2	Systemic illness				Intestinal obstruction	3	1.5	
a	Hypertension	8	4		Cleft lips	5	2.5	
b	Diabetes mellitus	2	1		Down's syndrome	11	5.5	
c	PUO	9	4.5		Others	10	5	
d	CHD	4	2	4	ABO+Rh. incompatibility	8	4	
e	Drug ingestion	19	9.5	5	Smoking	11	5.5	
f	Sever anemia	11	5.5		PUO. =pyrexia of unknown origin. C.H.D.=congenital heart disease			

Table (4): List of maternal risk categories associated with congenital intestinal obstruction

was present in 98 (49%) of case. Table (5) shows the leading symptoms and sign.

The commonest cause for congenital intestinal obstruction in the survey group as a whole, was an ano-rectal obstruction, which was found in 89 (44.5%) of the 200 cases. The next most common was gastric out-let obstruction, 31 (15.5%). The causes of congenital intestinal obstruction are displaced in table 5. Table -6 shows the number and percentage of the radiological study “conventional

and contrast “and other studies used for the elucidation the of diagnosis in this study.

Table-7 shows the types of congenital G.I.T obstruction by clinical, laboratories, and surgical findings. In males, an ano-rectal obstruction was responsible for 61(30.5%) of the cases , while in females it was responsible for 28 (14%) of the cases .the next most common cause in male group was gastric out-let obstruction ,24 (12 %) while the jejuno-ileal obstruction was the second cause in females 11(5.5%)of cases .

Table-8 shows the relative frequencies of each type of obstruction

Clinical presentation		No.ofcases
Vomiting	Total	133(66.4%)
	Bilious	88(44%)
	Non-bilious	37(18.5%)
	Blood stained	8(4%)
Failure to pass meconium		98(49%)
Abdominal distention		85(42.5%)
Feeding problems		55(27.5%)
Jaundice (total)		23(11.5%)
Respiratory distress		19(9.5%)
Intestinal pattering		9(4.5%)
Bowel sound		4(2%)
Abdominal pain, tenderness & crying		3(1.5%)
Bout of gastroenteritis/diarrhea		42(%)
Fever		3(1.5%)

Table (5): Leading signs and symptoms and clinical presentation

Diagnosis	Type	No (%).
Ultrasound	Prenatal	3(1.5%)
	Post natal	76(38%)
Radiography	Plain	163(81.5%)
	A contrast barium	40(20%)
Others	Rectal biopsies	15(7.5%)

Table (6): The number and percentage of the radiological study "conventional and contrast "and other studies used for the elucidation the diagnosis in this study.

There were associated anomalies in 87 patients from the total 200 (43.5 %) have one or more abnormalities other than the intestinal obstruction .The most common finding was the genitourinary 50 (25%). Table -9 shows the relative frequency of associated anomalies.

Types of obstructions	No	Male		Female	
Esophageal atresia	7(3.5%)	6	3%	1	0.5%
Gastric out-let obstruction	31(15.5%)	24	12%	7	3.5%
Duodenal obstruction	9(4.5%)	3	1.5%	6	3%
Jejuno-ileal obstruction	26(13%)	15	1.5%	11	5.5%
Meconium ileus	4(2%)	4	2%	-	-
Disorders of rotation and fixation	11(5.5%)	7	3.5%	4	2%
Obstruction of the colon	20(10%)	16	8%	4	2%
Ano-rectal obstruction	89(44.5%)	61	30.5%	28	14%
Others	2(1%)	1	0.5%	1	0.5%

Table (7): Types of congenital G.I.T obstruction by clinical, laboratories, and surgical findings.

The surgical operations which were done for these patients are shown in table-10. Enterostomy was the most common operation used in one form or another, 97 (48.5 percent) of total cases.The hospital stay period is dedicated in table -11. 200 operations were done with 44 postoperative deaths, (22%) of total cases .11 were discharged upon parents insistence, in 3 of these cases .it was almost certain that the patient was in a moribund condition, while the other 8 patients were doing well. 4 patients doing well but still required further surgical treatment at a later date. 141were discharged well (70.5 %). Thus if the 8 patients who were doing well but discharged at the parents request were added to those discharged well, the operation salvage rate would be 74.5 percent, with another high postoperative deaths, taken into consideration the 3

moribund cases that were discharged by parents 23.5%.

Esophageal atresia	No.	%	M	F
Without fistula	1	14.2	1	-
With proximal fistula	1	14.2	1	-
With distal fistula	5	71.4	4	1
Total	7		6	1
Gastric out-let obstruction	30	96.7	24	6
Hypertrophic pyloric stenosis				
Others	1	3.2	-	1
Total	31		24	7
Duodenal obstruction				
Type (1)	3	33.3		
Annular pancreas	6	66.6		
Total	9		3	6
Jejuno-ileal obstruction				
Type (1)	12	46.1		
Type (2)	6	23		
Type (3)	1	3.8		
Type (3)	5	19.2		
Others	2	7.6		
Total	26		15	11
Meconium ileus				
Uncomplicated	1	25	1	-
Complicated	3	75	3	-
Total	4		4	-
Incomplete rotation	6	54.5		
Incomplete fixation	1	9		
Others	4	36.3		
Total	11		7	4
Colonic obstruction				
Hirschsprungs disease	18	90		
Meconium plug syndrome	2	10		
Total	20		16	4
*High anorectal agenesis				
With fistula	39	43.8	5	5
Without fistula	18	20.2	13	5
Rectal atresia	3	3.3	2	1
Low anomaly				
With fistula	14	15.7	9	5
Without fistula	3	3.3	2	1
Anal stenosis	2	2.2	1	1
Persistent cloacae	10	11.2	-	10
	89		61	28

Table (8): The relative frequencies of each type of obstruction (The intermediate types were included in high anomaly, for both sexes)

Associated anomalies	No.(%)
Genitourinary	50(25%)
Urosepsis	7
Vesico-uretric fistula	11
Renal agenesis	4
Hours shoe kidney	2
Hypospadias	9
Urethral atresia	1
Polycystic kidney	2
Others.	7
Cardio-vascular	11(55%)
V.S.D.	5
A.S.D	3
Dextro cardia	2
Transposition of great vessels	1
Musculoskeletal	10(5%)
Polydactyl	2
Syndactaly	2
Talepus equinavarus	1
D.D.H	1
Others	4
Gastro-intestinal	7(35%)
Omphalocele	2
Cholydocal cyst	1
Others.	4
Respiratory	4(2%)
Choanal atresia	1
Others	3
Neurological: Hydrocephaly	1(05%)
Other	25(12.5%)
Down 's syndrome	10
Cystic fibrosis	2
Macrognothia	2
Cleft-lips	5
Cleft-palate	2
Polycystic liver	1
Tongue tie	1
Cataract	1
Fanconi's anemia	1

Table (9): Types and relative frequency of associated anomalies.

D.D.H: Developmental dysplasia of the hip.

V.S.D: Ventricular septal defect.

A.S.D: Atrial septal defect

Type of operation	No.	%
Enterostomy	97	48.5
Loop transverse colostomy	48	42
Descending colostomy	7	3.5
Ileostomy	6	3
Gastrostomy.	1	0.5
Intestinal anastomosis	37	18.5
Rammsted s pyloromyotomy	30	15
Anal dilation	2	1
Minimal posterior-sagittal	1	0.5
Postero-lateral thoractomy	6	3
Esophageal anastomosis		
Explorative laparotomy	5	2.5
Other operations	14	7

Table (10): Types of surgical procedures performed

The most common cause of death was septicemia which occurred in 34 % (15 of 44 deaths) of deaths postoperatively .the second commonest cause of in our study was multiple associated anomalies occurred in 18 percent (8 of 44 death) of deaths. The causes of death are listed in table-12.

The period in days	No.	%
Discharge on the same day	2	1
3 days	76	38
7 days	65	32.5
10 days	18	9
14 days	14	7
22days	13	6.5
30 days	9	4.5
> 30 days	3	1.5

Table (11): The hospital stay period

Causes	No.
Septicemia	15(34%)
Multiple anomalies	8(18%)
SIRS*	6(13.6%)
Respiratory failure	5(11.35%)
Progressive wasting	4(9%)
Aspiration pneumonia	3(6.8%)
Others	3(6.8%)
Total	44

Table (12): causes of deaths

The relative mortality rate in various congenital intestinal obstructions listed in table -13. Table -14 shows the relative frequency of complications that developed postoperatively in the survey group. These complications developed after the operative procedures and occurred in 49 (24.5%)' cases (died patient excluded here). Wound infection whether superficial or deep infections was the most frequent postoperative complications, 17 (8.5 %) of cases.

Type of obstructions	No.	% from total deaths	% from each type
Esophageal atresia	6	13.6	85.7
Meconium ileus	2	4.5	50
Others	1	2.2	50
Duodenal obstruction	4	9	44.4
Jejuno-ileal atresia	10	22.7	38.4
Malrotation	4	9	36.3
Hirschsprung's disease	5	11.2	25
Imperforate anus	10	22.7	11.2
Hypertrophic pyloric stenosis.	2	4.5	6.45
	44		

Table (13): The relative mortality rate in various congenital intestinal obstructions

Cause	No
Deaths	44(22%)
Wound infection	17(8.5%)
Septicemia	11(5.5%)
Wound dehiscence	9(4.5%)
Pneumonia	7(3.5%)
Anastomotic obstruction	3(1.5%)
Anastomotic leakage	2(1%)

Table (14): The relative frequency of post-operative complications

Discussion

Congenital intestinal obstruction is among the most common morbid condition need emergency surgery. It is encountered in children of any age, though most frequently in the neonatal period.

In this series 237 cases of congenital intestinal obstruction accounted for 3%, of the total hospital admission 8187. Thirty-seven cases were excluded from the study, because surgery was deemed unnecessary, unfit for surgery, parents requested discharge or were transferred to other units. Operations for congenital intestinal obstruction accounted 35% of all pediatric surgical operations performed.

The most common type of surgical procedure done for congenital intestinal obstruction was enterostomy accounting for 48.5% of the cases operated on and the most common form used is a transverse colostomy 42% of the cases most the transverse colostomies were done for neonate with a high imperforate anus and a Hirschsprung's disease as the first part of a staged operation for their treatment.

Maternal mortality ratio (MMR) in Baghdad Health Directorate-Risafa (BHD-R) Hospitals: 2002-2004

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Abstract

Background: The aim of this paper is to report the MMR in Risafa district hospitals during 3-year period.

Patients and methods: Data were collected from questionnaires completed and sent voluntarily to the Maternal and child (MCH) department by the attending obstetricians. Data were analyzed regarding the possible cause of death, type and place of delivery, age group and state of antenatal care attendance.

Results: 31 maternal deaths in hospitals were reported among 107605 hospital live births during the study period. MMR was estimated to be 28.8/ 100 000 live births. The leading direct cause of death was hemorrhage accounting for 65%, thromboembolism accounting for 13%, hypertensive disorders and early pregnancy complications.

Conclusion: The low MMR in this study is probably due to under-reporting and lower attendance rates. Priorities should be set towards a more accurate documentation and reporting of deaths in hospitals. Policies to reduce avoidable causes of death in terms of system support, training; and the adoption of international guidelines while formulating national guidelines.

Keywords: Maternal death, Maternal mortality ratio, Postpartum hemorrhage,

Pregnancy complications.

Introduction

In 2000, at least half a million women died from complications of pregnancy and childbirth, and other millions experienced morbidities. The maternal mortality ratio, which is a measure of the risk of death associated with each pregnancy was estimated to be 400 per 100 000 live births globally in 2000[1]. Causes of death were classified into: direct deaths resulting from obstetric complications of pregnancy; indirect deaths resulting from an existing disease aggravated by the physiologic effects of pregnancy; coincidental deaths resulting from unrelated causes which happen to occur in pregnancy or peripartum and late maternal deaths occurring between 42 days and 1 year from the end of pregnancy [2]. More than 70% of direct maternal deaths are due to avoidable causes namely: hemorrhage (25%), obstructed labor (8%), eclampsia (12%), sepsis (15%) or unsafe abortion (13%). [1]. Maternal mortalities reflect the quality and quantity of health services provided to the society and to the mothers during pregnancy and childbirth. The 1990 sanctions against Iraq accelerated a trend

of regression in health services in Iraq associated with inaccuracy of records and documentation, therefore transparent studies are needed to inform health policies and implement future programs. Such programs need measures of their efficiency. Maternal mortality ratio is one of these measures although it is not the only one.

Risafa district is the sector in Baghdad East to the River Tigris, which divides the city into 2 halves. The population in Risafa is 3,161,343.

Patients and methods

Data concerning maternal mortality were collected from all hospitals with maternity units affiliated to BHD-R for the period from January 1st, 2002 to December 31st, 2004. Seven hospitals were included in the study: 3 maternity hospitals and 4 general hospitals with labor rooms and wards. They were all comprehensive (level 2) obstetric care facilities according to the WHO classification of levels of care. A questionnaire was completed by the obstetrician attending the mother in hospital before death. The questionnaire was blinded for the deceased woman's name and attending obstetrician and sent to BHD-R /Maternal and Child Health (MCH) department, after group discussion in the hospital. Questionnaires were collected at the MCH department, blinded for the hospital and a copy sent to the Ministry of Health for information and documentation. Deaths not officially reported to the MCH-Department.

including deaths before reaching the hospitals were not included in the study. The total number of hospital live births during the 3 years was obtained from the department of health and vital statistics in BHD-R. The denominator was calculated as per 100 000 live births. Maternal mortality ratio (MMR) was calculated as: $MMR = \frac{\text{number of maternal deaths}}{100\,000 \text{ live births}}$. Each questionnaire was further analyzed to detect the possible cause of death, type of delivery, place of delivery, age group and antenatal attendance.

Results

107605 hospital live births and 31 maternal deaths were reported during the years 2002-2004. The MMR ratio for the years 2002-2004 was 28.80 per 100000 live births. Direct causes of deaths were present in 23 cases accounting for 75% of maternal deaths in series. Figure -1 shows the causes of maternal deaths. Half of the direct deaths (in 11 cases) were caused by post partum hemorrhage (PPH). Figure-2 shows the direct causes of maternal deaths.

Figure (1): The causes of maternal deaths Conclusion:

PPH=postpartum hemorrhage; APH=antepartum hemorrhage; HT= hypertensive disorders; EARLY PREG=early pregnancy complications namely abortions and ectopic pregnancy; GA=general anesthesia complications

Figure (2): The direct causes of maternal deaths.

Causes of deaths related to postpartum hemorrhage are shown in table-1. All deaths followed vaginal deliveries; in 9 cases occurred after home deliveries and in 2 cases occurred after hospital deliveries.

Cause of PPH	NUMBER	PERCENT
Inertia	3	27%
Multiple lacerations	3	27%
Rupture uterus	1	10%
Unknown cause	4	36%
Total	11	100%

Table (1): Deaths from PPH matched with the cause of PPH.

The range of time spent in hospital for women with postpartum hemorrhage was 0.15-6.0 hours (Average time was 2.20 hours) .The number of blood units transfused to the women with bleeding

between hospital admission and death are shown in table-2.

Number	Units transfused	Duration between hospital admission & death
1	no blood	20 minutes
2	2 units	1 hour
3	5-6 unit	5-6 hours
5	not mentioned	10 min.-3 hours

Table 2: Number of blood units transfused to the women before death from PPH matched with the duration between hospital admission and death.

The 4 mothers who died from antepartum hemorrhage (APH) had preterm pregnancies, delivered by cesarean section, 3 of them had morbid adhesions of placenta and were more than 35 years of age. Magnesium sulphate was not mentioned nor used and

diazepam was used instead, for those who died of hypertension

Among the indirect causes of maternal deaths 2 of them were due to jaundice complications .The cause of death was not mentioned nor identified. Half the maternal deaths including those who died from bleeding were under 35 years old Table -3.Only one report mentioned regular antenatal care during pregnancy and there were no referrals of women in complicated labors from primary health care facilities to neither comprehensive obstetric care facilities nor tertiary referral hospitals.

Age group	Death from any cause		Death from bleeding	
	N	%	N	%
<25 years	7	23%	3	20%
25-29	5	16%	3	20%
30-34	6	19%	1	7%
35-39	6	19%	5	33%
>40 yrs.	4	13%	2	13%
Unknown age	3	10%	1	7%
Total	31	100%	15	100%

Table 3: number of maternal deaths according to the age group

Discussion

The low MMR noticed in this study (28.8/100000 live births) resulted probably from under-reporting and lower tendency to refer. Numbers from previous international studies were about 10 times this number. These studies were based on the sisterhood method [3] of calculating maternal deaths [table-4]. In our study the methodology is different- it is a facility based study, however the results are relatively comparable to a recent study published in Iraq in cooperation with the WHO table-4 , and

makes mortality ratios in Iraq relatively comparable to maternal mortality ratios in other Middle Eastern countries like Turkey ,Egypt and Iran (table 5).Though this study reflects a mortality ratio in a certain district in Baghdad, it is not conclusive for Iraq and further studies are needed to calculate the mortality ratios in other parts of Iraq collectively and regionally.

The number of deaths is under reported for the following reasons:

The reporting was not obligatory and probably not all deaths were reported to the MCH dept.

The deaths outside delivery rooms were not reported to MCH dept. I.e. hospital deaths of women referred to dialysis units, ICU or RCU as well as community deaths outside hospitals.

There was a relative decrease in death reporting for the year 2003 which may be explained by the chaos that followed the 2003 war. The number of women who died before reaching hospitals might never be known.

The same problems for deficient reporting pointed out by the WHO stand for this study; namely inaccuracies in routine registers ,omission of deaths other than in maternity wards ,inaccurate case records and difficulty in retrieving records for reviews [3].

Avoidable factors constitute 83% of direct causes of maternal deaths (namely bleeding, hypertensive complications and early pregnancy problems).

Analysis regarding the mode of delivery showed that all deaths from PPH followed vaginal deliveries (n=11) contrasts the confidential enquiry into maternal deaths in the UK for the years 1994-1996 [4] where all deaths from PPH followed operative deliveries and interventions.

Yr	MMR/100000 live births	Methodology	Reference and year of publication
1999	294	Sisterhood method	Maternal, child and reproductive health strategy in Iraq 2005-2008/2005 ,(MOH,WHO,UNICEF,UNFPA)
2000	250	Not mentioned	The world health report 2005, ANNEX 8, P.212 .WHO.
2006-2007	47 / past 5 years 84 / past 15 years	Sisterhood method	Iraq Family health Survey report /JAN.2008 (MOH,MOPDC,WHO Iraq)
2002-2004	28.8	Facility based study	Our study

Table (4): List of previous studies of MMR done in Iraq in cooperation with international organizations.

COUNTRY	MMR/100 000 live births
Iran	76
Turkey	70
Egypt	84

**Table (5): MMR in some Middle Eastern countries nearby Iraq.
Ref.: The world health report 2005, ANNEX 8, P.212 .WHO.**

The majority of deaths from PPH followed home deliveries (9/11) and the rapid deaths within less than 1 hour (6/11) indicate a delay in bringing the woman to hospital whether be it by the family or birth attendant.

It was evident that all the women who died from bleeding were not transfused adequately .The amount of blood loss was either underestimated or the bleeding was not detected early, rapidly assessed ,adequately transfused and timely managed for the cause of bleeding. Delays in immediate mobilization of the blood product preparation and transfusion system may have happened and O negative blood is not always available.

The fact that- 30% of a pregnant woman's blood volume can be lost before circulatory decompensation

appears [5], explains why moderate blood loss is compensated in pregnancy and after delivery, as well as heavy loss is underestimated.

Around 1000-1500 milliliters of blood can be lost within 10 minutes of delivery [6] .This fact &" the four T's" of the causes of post partum hemorrhage (tone, tissue, trauma & thromboses) [5, 6] should be kept in mind & recognized by the medical staff in hospital as well as the birth attendant at home and even by the woman's family to avoid delay in referral from home or in action taking in hospital.

It is well recognized that the risk of maternal death increases with advancing age over 35 years [7]. However in this study 40% of women who were below the age of 35, died from bleeding which means that there is still a good potential to decrease the mortality in the younger-usually healthy group of women.

The use of magnesium sulphate was not mentioned in the management of women who died from hypertensive disorders probably because of lack of magnesium blood level measurement, fear of overdose or unavailability of drug in the hospital. Diazepam was used instead.

.This reflects the need for permanent provision of magnesium sulphate in all labor suits in hospitals because it is the first line drug in the prevention and treatment of severe hypertensive disorders of pregnancy

The observation that only one woman had regular antenatal care shows that this important sector is not playing its role in risk detection and referral from the low risk antenatal care clinics.

No woman who had labor complications was referred from a primary health care (PHC), level 1 facility. This reflects in part the insecurity, instability and lack of motivation that drives doctors to deliver women in level 1 facilities. What can be read from this , is that the birth attendant at home - who is not always a skilled one and is usually a permanent resident in the area , is doing the job instead , and may explain the multitude of late referrals of women with postpartum hemorrhage . This highlights the need to improve the skills of certified home birth attendants in risk detection and referral.

The key indicator of service provision is the coverage of labors and deliveries by skilled birth attendants. On the long run one can benefit from other nation's experience in providing skilled assistance by professionalization of midwifery & gradually phasing out of the unskilled traditional birth attendant [8, 9]. Provision of skilled birth attendants for all is a goal not to be achieved overnight. It took 10 -20 years in some developing countries like Malaysia and Sri Lanka to name a few .However the impact on maternal mortality became evident even before skilled birth attendance became accessible to all women. In some cases the impact of skilled birth attendance became discernible when the coverage was only 40 % although to sustain the

reductions in maternal mortality, it was imperative to continue to increase the coverage [11].

The quality of care needs to be addressed and improved .Estimates of ratios from 50-250/100 000 may point to problems of quality of care for labor and delivery while higher ratios, suggest problems of access [11], and this stands true for this study.

Acquiring knowledge and eventually skills should be based on clinical standards and guidelines based on the best available evidence and trainers need to teach the same set of evidence-based information for the most frequently occurring complications of pregnancy to allow acquisition of skills on a national basis.

Fire-drill practice scenarios would be of help maintaining the skills and practice inside hospitals for some pregnancy complications like PPH and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy [6, 12].

Transferring skills into practice is complex task and requires an adequate hospital setting with available equipment, drugs ,blood and trained personnel all times of the year and an infra structure capable of achieving the continuity and maintenance of this goal .

Conclusion: Priorities should be set towards more accurate documentation and reporting of deaths in hospitals. Avoidable causes of death are still a major cause of death like in other developing countries and measures need to be taken to decrease them in terms of system support, training programs, adopting guidelines or adapting already existing ones and provision of skilled birth attendance for all women in labor at the community level.

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Ampullary carcinoma in Iraqi patients: Single center experience

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Abstract

Background: The aim of this paper is to report the pattern of ampullary carcinoma in Iraqi patients.

Patients and methods: During the period 1995-2000, 106 patients with ampullary carcinoma were admitted to Gastroenterology tertiary center accounting for 2% of the total admission and 9% of gastrointestinal malignancies. 64 (60.4%) were male and 42 (39.6%) were females. 97 (87%) male are affected 1.5 times more than female with male: female ratio = 1.5. Age peak incidence bet(50-59) .

Results: Patients came mainly from Baghdad 46% .Presenting symptom were jaundice in 78.3% Duration of illness the peak is 1-2 months mean period is (45 days) for lab investigations.

Of the 85 patients. who undergone operation, resection was performed in 56 patients (66%) . Thirty patients had radical resection (Whipple procedure: pancreaticoduodenectomy) and 26 patients had local resection. The tumor was adenocarcinoma in all the cases. Only one case was undifferentiated carcinoma.

Conclusion: The pattern of ampullary carcinoma is slightly different from the previous reports.

Keywords: Ampullary carcinoma, Pattern, Iraq.

Introduction

Carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater is defined as a malignant tumor arising in the last centimeter of the common bile duct where it passes through the wall of the duodenum and ampullary papilla. The pancreatic duct (of Wirsung) and common bile duct merges and exits by way of the ampulla into the duodenum. .

Carcinoma originating in the ampulla of Vater by gross inspection can arise from any one of 4 epithelial types: (1) terminal common bile duct; (2) duodenal mucosa; (3) pancreatic duct and (4) ampulla of Vater[1- 8]

Patients and Methods

106 patients with ampullary carcinoma were observed in GIT CENTER (tertiary center) during the period from January 1995 to December 2000. During that period total admission was 5416 cases, 1186 of them were having GIT malignancies. Management of these cases was either totally in the GIT Center or might be partially in the GIT Center and partially in other hospitals including Baghdad Teaching Hospital and the Nursing Home.

Preoperative laboratory studies included complete blood picture, blood urea, serum creatinine, serum electrolyte, fasting blood sugar, prothrombin time, partial thromboplastin time and liver function tests.

Other investigations include fasting blood sugar prothrombin time partial thromboplastin time blood urea and serum creatinine were also done preoperatively, blood sugar was recorded for 45 patients eight of them had blood sugar above 120 mg/dl. Some had additional investigations like HBs Ag, alpha fetoprotein, serum protein electrophoresis, HbsAg was positive in five patients out of 25 estimated.

Abdominal ultrasound was performed in all the patients. ERCP was done in 93 cases and biopsies were taken from all patients. CT was done in two patients only. MRI was done in only five patients. PTC. were done in two patients. Cholecystostomy under local anesthesia was done for one patient. Endoscopic stenting was done for 12 patients.

Results

106 patients with ampullary carcinoma represented 2% of the total admissions to the GIT Center during this period (5416 patients), and 9% of the GIT malignancies. 64 of them were males. Previous operations include cholecystotomy in 17 patients (16%). Operation for hydatid cyst endocystotomy for 7 patients 6.6%, splenectomy 1 patient 0.9% and ureteric stone in one patient 0.9%.

The age ranged between 18-92 years with mean age of 56.8 years and a peak incidence of 50-59 years (Figure 1).

About half of the patients (49%) were from Baghdad. There 8 were patients from Anbar,7 from Diala, 6 from Salahuddin, 5 from Babel,5 from Karbala,5 from Kirkuk,21 patients from another 8 provinces. Jaundice was the most common presenting symptom [Table-1] occurring in 78.3% followed by palpable gall bladder in 61.3%, loss of weight encountered only in 33% of patients. Itching was present in 44.3% one patient presented as fever 0.9% and 1 patient presented as malena 0.9%. Eight patients were diabetic, six patients had ischemic heart disease and 17 patients were hypertensive.

Figure (1): Age distribution

Duration of symptoms (Table-2) ranged between 10 days and 1 year with a peak between 1-2 months, mean period was 45 days. in 24 patients, 12.1-14 in 41 patients and 14.1-16 in 15 patients.

Presenting symptom	Number of patients	%
Fever, rigor	28	26
Abdominal pain	52	49
Jaundice	83	78.3
Loss of weight	35	33
Palpable mass (gall bladder)	65	61.3
Pruritis	47	44.3
Palpable mass	4	3.7
Fever	1	0.9
Malena	1	0.9

Table (1): Presenting symptom

Duration	Patients	%
< 2 weeks	21	19.8
2-4 weeks	25	23.5
1-2 month	32	30.1
2-3 month	9	8.4
4 month	7	6.6
4-6 month	2	1.8
6-12 month	7	6.6
> 1 year	3	2.8
Total	106	100

Table (2): Duration symptoms

Hemoglobin level (g/dl)	No	%
< 8	3	2.8
8.1-10	23	21.6
10.1-12	24	22.6
12.1-14	41	38.6
14.1-16	15	14.1
ESR (Mm/hr.)		
5-19	23	21.4
20-49	23	21.6
50-100	45	42.4
> 100	15	14.6
Bilirubin level (mg/dl)		
< 1.2	20	18.8
1.3-3	5	4.7
3.1-6	18	17
6.1-10	14	13.2
10.1-20	34	32
20-30	12	11.3
> 30	3	2.8
Alkaline phosphatase		
> 13 (KA)	14	13.2
13-20	19	17.2
21-30	34	32
31-40	18	16.9
41-50	15	14.3
> 50	6	5.6
SGPT (IU/l)		
10-45	48	45
46-60	27	25.7
60-100	19	18
> 100	12	11.3
SGOT (IU/l)		
10-45	48	45
46-60	30	28.5
61-100	26	24.5
> 100	2	2

Table (3) Laboratory investigations.

Laboratory investigations is shown in table-3. Hemoglobin below 8 g/dl found in three patients only, (8.1-10) in 23 patients, between 10.1-12 (60.4%) and 42 were females with male to female ratio equal to 1:1.52. TSB was normal in 20 patients(18.8%) .TSB was between 10-20 mg/dl (in 34 patients 32%). Liver was found to be normal in 40 patients (37.7%). Hepatomegaly was found in 66 patients (62.2%) .Dilated intrahepatic duct (IHD) was found in 88 patients(83%). Liver secondaries were found in 4 patients (3.7%).ERCP finding: Fungating tumor of ampulla in 38 patients, ulcerated ampulla in 20 patients, bleeding from ampulla in 15 patients, abnormal ampulla in 15 patients, duodenal mass in 3 patients duodenal obstruction in 2 patients.

ESR was elevated in 78.6% of the patients it range between (50-100mm/hr) in 83 patients. Liver enzymes SGOT and SGPT were elevated in 55%. Alkaline phosphatase was elevated in 86.6% of the cases .

Ultrasound findings : Gall bladder was normal in 26 patients (24.5%), 17 patients had cholecystectomy (16%),and 63 patients (59.5%) had distended gall bladder, 6 patients of them had gall bladder stones. Common bile duct (CBD) was normal in 3 patients 2.8%, dilated in 103 patients (97.2%), and tumor was found in 38 patients (35%).Dilated pancreatic duct was found in 25 patients (23.5%).

Sensitivity was found to be 100% in ERCP in the diagnosis of Ampullary mass compared to 35.8% in ultrasound as shown in table- 4. Dilated common bile duct (CBD) was 100% accurate in ERCP compared to 97.1% in ultrasound. IHD dilated was 100% in ERCP compared to 83% in ultrasound.

Pancreatic duct was found to be dilated in 23.5% in ultrasound compared to 15% in ERCP.

Pathology	Ultrasound		ERCP	
	No	%	No	%
Ampullary mass	38	35.8	93	100
Common bile duct dilatation	103	97.1	93	100
IHD dilatation	88	83	93	100
Pancreatic duct dilatation	25	23.5	14	15
Overall sensitivity	93	87.7	93	100

Table (4): Sensitivity of ultrasound and ERCP

Operative findings : Gall bladder was distended in 64%, removed in 16% and normal in 20%.CBD. was dilated in all patients 100%. Liver secondaries were found in eight cases.

Of the 85 patients. who undergone operation, resection was performed in 56 patients (66%) . Thirty patients had radical resection (Whipple procedure: pancreaticoduodenectomy) and 26 patients had local resection. The tumor was adenocarcinoma in all the cases. Only one case was undifferentiated carcinoma.

58.4% of the patients who survived at 2 year have tumors less than 2 cm, and 33.3% have tumor 2-4 cm only and only 8.3% of them have tumor >4cm. 50% have well differentiated, 33.3% have moderately differentiated and 16.7% have poorly differentiated carcinoma

Only one patients with resectable tumor and well-differentiated carcinoma survived for 5 years and the tumor was less than 2 cm. Table -5 shows tumor size and grade in 85 patients. Table -6) shows tumor size, grading and survival.

Tumor size (85 patients)	No of patients	Parentage %
< 2 cm	18	21.1
2-4 cm	58	68.2
> 4 cm	9	10.7
Grade		
Poorly differentiated	9	8.5
Moderately differentiated	67	63.2
Well differentiated	30	28.3

differentiated

Table (5) :Tumor size and grade in the 85 patients.

Follow up in years	< 2 cm	2-4 cm
2 years	7 (58.4%)	4 (33.3%)
5 years	1 (100%)	0
Survival (years)	Well differentiated	Moderately differentiated
2 years	6 (50%)	4 (33.3%)
5 years	1 (100%)	0

Table (6) Tumor size, grading and survival.

Palliative procedures were performed in 29 patients with different type of bypass operations because the tumor was beyond resection. Palliative procedures included choledochoduodenostomy in 4 patients , cholecystojejunostomy plus gastrojejunostomy in 12 patients ,choledochojejunostomy in 4 patients ,cholecystojejunostomy alone in 5

patients ,gastrojejunostomy in 1 patient, 3 patients had only biopsy during laparotomy. Postoperative mortality in bypass surgery was 1 out of 29 patients (3.4%).It was possible to follow 17 patients of the 29 patients , 6 of the was still living at 2 years ,non was alive at 5 years.

In surgical resection is 8 out of 56 patients. 2 out of 26 patients (7%) patients died after local resection while of 30 patients who undergone Whipple procedure 6 die (20%). It was possible to follow 23 patients of the 56, 12 were alive at 2 year and 10 all of them had undergone Whipple procedure were alive at 5 year. Table-7 shows the :postoperative complications.

Type of operation	Complication	No of patients	Mortality
Whipple procedure	Bleeding	3	1 died
	Septicemia	3	1 died
	Uremia	4	2 died
	Fistula	4	1 died
	Myocardial infarction	2	1 died
Local resection	Fistula	3	1 died
	Bleeding	2	1 died
	Septicemia	1	
Palliative procedure	Myocardial infarction	1	1 died
	Wound infection	1	
	Fistula	1	
	Cholangitis	1	

Table (7) :Postoperative complications.

In addition 12 patients had endoscopic stenting,1 patient had cholecystostomy (under local anesthesia), and 2 patients had PTCD.6 patients refused surgery. Those patients who underwent endoscopic stenting, local cholecystostomy and PTCD. were in

advanced stage or unfit for general anesthesia or both.

12 patients received various schedules of 5-fluorouracil, Adriamycin / or mitomycin postoperatively.

Two patients with surgical biliary bypass came back with duodenal obstruction that needed gastroenterostomy. Cholecystostomy under local anesthesia was done on only one case, which was uremic, and had ischemic heart disease and could not tolerate general anesthesia. Twelve patients had undergone endoscopic stenting because the tumor was advanced and six patients refused surgery. Two patients had only PTCD.

	This study %	[10] %	[9] %
Weight loss	33	69	90
Abdominal mass	9	6	5
Pain	49	38	81
Jaundice	78.3	88	73
Anorexia	45	30	43
Palpable gall bladder	61	50	42
Malaise	32	30	35
Melaena	0.9	0	0
Fever	0.9	0	0
Prurits	44.3	37	32
Cholangitis	25	21	30

Table (8):The most common presenting symptom

Discussion

The incidence Ampullary carcinoma peaked at 50-59 years while peaked at 61-70 in some previous reports [9].The male to female ration was 1.52 in this study while it was 1.1 to 1.2 in some previous reports[1,9]. The most common presenting symptom was jaundice, which accounting for 78.3% in this series while this was slightly higher in western studies [9].

Complication rate following Whipple operation remained high (53.3%) in this study. Cameron reported a lower rate o between 30-35%. Pancreatic fistula was the most serious one; it was 10% in this study. Cameron study reported a rate between 5-20%.

Pancreatic fistula usually associated with high mortality rate which was 33% in this study while in Cameron study was 10-40%. Postoperative length of stay in hospital in our study average was 14 days. Blood transfusion was more. The average was 4 units while in Cameron study was between 1.27-1.35% units.

Conclusion: The pattern of ampullary carcinoma is slightly different from the previous reports.

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Surgical management of carpal tunnel syndrome: Open release and endoscopic release

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to review the surgical management of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS), comparing the Open Carpal Tunnel Release (OCTR) versus the Endoscopic Carpal Tunnel Release (ECTR).

Literatures reported that both techniques achieved resolution in the preoperative symptoms in most of the patients. ECTR Results in earlier return to work (median 14 vs. 28 days), less scar tenderness (64% vs. 39%), less nerve neurapraxia (average (5.75% vs. 10%), less flexor tendon bowstringing and cosmetically more acceptable results.

ECTR was found to be a demanding technique (hat required a well trained hand surgeon. when it is contraindicated or can not be done, OCTR still provides an effective and safe alternative.

Keywords: Carpal Tunnel Syndrome, Surgical management, Techniques.

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS) is the most common, the most important, the best defined and the most carefully studied of all nerve entrapment syndromes. It can be defined as compression of the median nerve within Confines of the tunnel created by the transverse carpal ligament and the carpal

bones. Characterized by pain and parasthesia in the distal median nerve distribution. The diagnosis is easily established clinically and early treatment by division of transverse carpal ligament results in complete cure, delay can result in irreversible median nerve damage.

It was estimated that the incidence of carpal tunnel surgery is between 400,000 and 500.000 cases annually in the United States with economic costs in excess of 2 billions U.S. dollars per year.

The costs incurred in worker's compensation cases are almost five times those of non workers [1, 2, 3].

Open Carpal Tunnel Release (OCTR)

The symptoms of carpal tunnel syndrome are relived when the median nerve in the carpal tunnel is completely decompressed. Surgical decompression of the median nerve by sectioning the transverse carpal ligament is a simple operative procedure that promises the patient's relief from pain and parasthesia.

Phalen, 1972 [4] on operating on 215 hands, demonstrated that thenar atrophy of greater or lesser degree was present in 110 hands. Seven of those 110 hands with atrophy had a follow up examination of less than 6 months. Of the other 103 hands, 86 regained normal thenar muscle. 9 showed various degrees

of improvements in thenar muscle power. 7 showed no improvement, and there was progression of thenar atrophy in one hand.

Of the 215 surgically treated hands. 9 had a follow-up study of less than 6 months Of the 206 adequately followed surgically treated hands, 147 (718%) regained normal sensation post operatively, 57 hands (27.6%) were improved but still had some impaired sensation in the median nerve distribution, 2 hands in 2 patients were not improved [4].

Adams et.al ,1994[5] on performing OCTR for 191 hands and following them up for a mean of 3 years post operatively for clinical, disability, and return to work outcomes.

They noticed that the relief of pain was complete or modest in 86%, and only 14% of cases reported no improvement in symptoms. Mean duration of disability (time loss) postoperatively was nearly 4 months, and 8% of cases exceeded one year of time loss.

The majority of cases returned to their same job (67%), or to a different job (15%) Workers in high risk occupations were less likely to return to the same job after OCTR compared to those in lower risk occupations (61% vs. 75%) and they concluded that in this population, no association was seen between any outcome and age, gender, marital status, or baseline wage [5].

To review comprehensively the results of the direct visualization method of decompression of the carpal tunnel. Thurston and Lam. 1997 [6] assessed the patients perceptions of (he seventy of pain, numbness and parasthesia due to carpal tunnel syndrome before and after OCTR in 188 hands which were reviewed retrospectively at a minimum time of follow-up of 18 months.

Motor and sensory testing, provocation testing, and measurement of scar tenderness in 135 hands were reviewed. They demonstrated that 70% experienced reduction in the severity of pain after OCTR. 78% of hands experienced a reduction in the severity of parasthesia and 77% experienced a reduction in the severity of numbness. 49% had improvement in all three symptoms after OCTR.

At the clinical review, sensory testing revealed that 59% of hands had normal or slightly diminished light touch. 35% had normal static two points discrimination, and results for Tinel's sign, Phalen's test .and pressure provocation testing were positive in 10% of hands.

There was no scar tenderness in 38%, no persisting thenar atrophy in 90%. Normal grip strength was found in 93% and 91 % had normal pinch strength.

On reviewing 60 cases retrospectively for an average of 5.5 years after OCTR. Nancollas et.al. 1995 demonstrated that 87% of cases reported a good or excellent overall outcome; the average time to maximum improvement of symptoms was 9.8 months.

However, 30% reported poor to fair strength and long term scar discomfort, and 57% noted a return of some pre-operative symptoms, most commonly pain, beginning an average of 2 years after surgery. They found no correlation between pre-operative symptoms or extent of surgical dissection (Neurolysis) and outcome.

Carpal tunnel syndrome was job related in 42%, of these, 26% changed from heavy to lighter work following surgery. Although occupational cases were slower to improve and remained out off work longer, the long term subjective results were the same for both groups, they found significant morbidity from

the surgical scar and decreased strength, and often considerable delay until ultimate improvement, specialty in patients with job-related carpal tunnel syndrome.

Citron and Bendall [6], 1997 they studied the local symptoms after open carpal tunnel release in a prospective trial involving 47 patients. The results can be demonstrated in the following figures regarding the post operative grip strength, thenar and hypothenar tenderness and scar sensitivity.

Endoscopic Carpal Tunnel Release (ECTR)

Endoscopic Carpal Tunnel Release (ECTR) is a most controversial discussed procedure not only among surgeons but among patients as well.

ECTR was evaluated in many studies to determine its value in treating carpal tunnel syndrome, and whether it limits postoperative morbidity without posing unacceptable risks.

Agee et al, 1992[6] studied 97 patients who had unilateral release and 25 had bilateral release of the transverse carpal ligament. All of them had the diagnosis of idiopathic carpal tunnel syndrome with abnormal nerve conduction studies, but normal electromyograms. Conventional open surgery was done in 65 hands whereas 82 were treated with the ECTR device. Forty nine of 79 patients who worked were treated with this device.

Results showed that post operative strength and tenderness were the best predictors of the return to work and daily activities (Tables 1,2,3,4) The time to return to work was shorter in patients treated with the ECTR device. when those not given worker's compensation where analyzed after unilateral surgery, patients returned to work in an average of 16.5 days, compared with 45.5 days

for control patients. Three fourths of patients in the ECTR-treated group returned to work within 42 days, but 52 days were needed for the same proportion of control patients to resume working. Patients not on workers compensation resumed daily activities on an average of 5 days after surgery with the new device and 13days after conventional surgery. Two device-treated patients were re-operated on by open decompression. Two others had transient ulnar neurapraxia.

They concluded that the ECTR device promotes an earlier return to work and daily activities in patients treated for carpal Tunnel syndrome [6].

Menon in 1993 evaluated 100 patients who undergone endoscopic carpal tunnel release with the single portal technique, showed that 94% had resolution of symptoms. None of the patients suffered permanent disability as a result of ECTR. Furthermore, 76% of patients regained 100% or more of their preoperative grip strength within 4 weeks after operation [7].

In a single group prospective study, using the single portal endoscopic carpal tunnel release system, Elmaraghy and Hurst, 1996 operated on 86 hands in 69 patients. They followed up the patients at 10 days and 6 and 10 weeks postoperatively all cases were performed by the same surgeon.

The subjective symptoms of CTS, including parasthesia, numbness and pain, demonstrated substantial improvement by 10 days postoperatively and less than 2% of the subjects remained symptomatic by 10 weeks.

Preoperative grip and three-point pinch strength were regained by 6 weeks post operatively.

Workers compensation cases required a significantly longer time to return to

work (mean 40.8 days) than non workers compensation cases (mean 22.2 days).

No difference, however, was demonstrated between worker's compensation and non worker's compensation cases with respect to the time of return to activities of daily living (mean 13.5 days). There were no major neurovascular injuries but there was one mild reflex sympathetic dystrophy, three transient neurapraxia and one superficial wound infection [8].

To assess the efficacy and safety of the two portal Chow technique of ECTR. Roth et al, 1994[9] operated on 94 patients (35men, 59 women) with a total of 108 surgical procedures.

The results showed that the average preoperative duration of symptoms was 3.9 years. Nerve conduction studies were positive in 101 of the 108 hands. Only two patients required open release. Six patients failed to obtain relief of symptoms; two of them required secondary open release owing to persistent symptoms. Of the 61 patients who were employed, 52 returned to their previous jobs without restriction. The mean time for return to work was 36.4 days for patients who were workers compensation board cases and 19.5 days for patients who were not. Men returned to work in 17.7 days, and women in 24 7 days. Complications occurred in four patients (3.8%).No nerve injury, vascular injury or reflex sympathetic dystrophy was noted.

Patients who had undergone previous contralateral open release noted less pain and earlier return to work after ECTR.

They concluded that ECTR was effective in relieving symptoms and had a low complication rate. The technique was associated with early return to work and minimal palmer pain [9].

In a review of 208 cases by Armstong et al, [10] using the Chow two portal

technique. They operated on 149 patients , 90 had unilateral and 59 bilateral procedures the age of the patients ranged from 30 to 86 years with a mean age of 50.5 years.

The male to female sex ratio was 1:3.3 .and 94 left hands and 114 right hands were treated. The follow up period ranged from 3 to 34 months.

Post operatively 67% of patients considered the operation to have been successful without any persistence of the preoperative symptoms of carpal tunnel syndrome However, 32% reported that their symptoms did persist, with some patients suffering from more than one residual symptom as seen in table-1.

Symptom	Number of hands	
	Preoperative	Postoperative
Pain	185(89%)	37(18%)
Numbness	160(77%)	12(6%)
Weakness	156(75%)	27(13%)
Parasthesia	195(94%)	35(17%)
Stiffness	174(84%)	25(12%)

Table-1

On investigations about the incidence of iatrogenic nerve complications in the endoscopically operated patients six hands (29%) had post operative numbness which was not present before surgery.

Of these, four hands (19%) had a transient neurapraxia which had resolved at the time of completing the follow up. but in two cases the situation was permanent. Both these patients complained of decreased sensation in (tie distribution of the common digital nerve to the ring and middle fingers

The permanent iatrogenic, nerve complication rate was 0.9% (2/208) No other serious complications occurred. There was no case of re-operation for incomplete division of the flexor retinaculum [10].

Carpal tunnel syndrome is a commonly occurring entrapment neuropathy of the median nerve at the wrist until late 80s; OCTR was simple, effective surgical procedure that relieves the symptoms of CTS.

But now since endoscopic surgery is increasingly requested in many branches of surgery by a population which is more aware of treatment options than ever before.

Endoscopic division of the flexor retinaculum is an established technique in the surgical repertoire.

In a prospective randomized comparative study Brown et.al [11], compared the results of OCTR with that of two portal ECTR on 169 hands in 145 patients. Follow up evaluations were performed at 21, 42 and 84 days at the end of follow up period. Both open and endoscopic methods had resulted in high level of achievement of the primary outcomes (relief of pain and parasthesia). Symptoms relief were in eighty (98%) of 82 hands in OCTR group compared with 77(99%) of 78 hands in ECTR group, the open technique resulted in more tenderness of the scar than did the endoscopic method.

Thirty-two (39%) of OCTR group and fifty (64%) of ECTR group were not tender at 84 days (These parameters were not recorded for 3 hands in open release group and 6 hands in ECTR group).

The open method also resulted in a longer interval until the patient could return to work (Median, 28 days, compared with 14 days for ECTR group).

The patient's satisfaction with the procedure, graded on a scale of 0 to 100%. averaged 84% in the OCTR group. Compared with 89% in the group that had had endoscopic release.

Palmer et.al in 1993[12], were the first to conduct a comparative prospective study to compare three different treatment methods; standard open method, a single portal endoscopic technique (Agee), and a two portal endoscopic technique (Chow). Two hundred eleven releases in 163 patients were evaluated and followed up for 6-months period. There was no difference in resolution of symptoms between treatment methods. Patients treated with open release reported more thumb weakness and pain with activities of daily living after surgery. Endoscopically treated patients achieved faster recovery of grip and pinch strength and wrist range of motion. They also had less mid-palm tenderness than did patients treated via OCTR, and Agee patients had less distal palmar tenderness than did patients treated via other methods.

Overall, and in the workers compensation group. Patients treated endoscopically returned to work sooner. In the non workers compensation group, Agee patients returned to work sooner than did patients treated via the other two methods.

Richter and Bruser in 1996 [13], comparing the results of long palm incision with those found by Agee et.al [6] demonstrated that the long incision led to temporary 10% loss of strength only during the first 3 weeks. These results should be kept in mind in the light of occasionally severe neurovascular complications following ECTR.

The weakness in grip strength is a recognized complication of CTS surgeries which is due to flexor tendons bowstringing at the carpal canal. This found to be greater after ECTR than that in intact wrists, but less than after OCTR.

This is true in both a 0° to 70° flexion range and for the full 140 flexion-

extension arc. Less consumption of flexor tendon excursion with wrist motion means better mechanical efficiency after ECTR compared with open release. Brown et.al [14].

An other advantage of ECTR is that it promotes earlier return to work and daily activities because this procedure decreases the post-operative morbidity attributable to the division of the overlying palmar Fascia, Fat and skin. So it is associated with less scar tenderness (Agee et.al. 1992).

Although ECTR is becoming an established technique. However, many surgeons view it as an unnecessarily complicated operation which is not without serious potential complications including nerves injuries. Median nerve neurapraxia varies from 2.5% to 10% in patients treated by single portal ECTR [6, 14], and from 7.5% to 13% when double portal technique is used [14].

Schenck [15], reported a multicentre retrospective survey of ECTR in the United States, in which over 4600 endoscopic procedures using the Chow technique were evaluated; the overall permanent nerve injury rate was 0.8%.

The permanent decrease in sensation of the common digital nerve to the ring and middle fingers could have resulted from stretching, compression, or division of the communicating branch between the median and ulnar nerve in the palm which tends to occur when the communicating nerve is located at the distal margin of the flexor retinaculum- (Armstrong et al, 1997) [10].

Using the Chow technique, Thomas et al reported 2 ulnar artery lacerations and 10 cases of transient parasthesia in the 3rd web space in 150 cases While Worseg et.al. [16] reported a 5% incidence of transient parasthesia in the 3rd web space using the single portal technique

However; it has also been reported in OCTR [17].

Povlsen et.al [18], reported no neurological complications such as pillars pain, paraesthesia, digital nerves injuries and scar tenderness. They attribute this to the use of Agee technique and they suggests that there is a difference between the incidence of complications of the double and single portal methods as these techniques are distinctly different.

The method described by Chow requires, a prolonged maximal extension of the wrist which generates a very high pressure in the carpal tunnel even before the endoscope introduction.

They concluded that it is possible that some of the complications following release with Chow method which have been reported as incomplete nerve divisions could have been iatrogenic crush injuries Pillars pain and parasthesia was not related solely to the incision of the skin, it may be a combined effect of reversible changes in the central processing of low threshold mechanoreceptive input both from the carpal ligament and the palmar skin [19, 20].

Damage to major or digital nerves has always been regarded as an unacceptable complication of OCTR, although they have no doubt occurred without being widely publicized [12], reported transient neurapraxia in 10% of patients when an open technique was used.

Kuschner et al [21], in a literature review of over 3000 open cases reported an overall complications rate of 9.2% including a permanent nerve injury rate of 0.8% The key finding reported by Povlsen et.al [18] reported that single portal endoscopic division of the carpal ligament, when used by surgeons with previous experience in arthroscopy and on carefully selected patients, can

significantly reduce the development of pillars pain and parasthesia the pain threshold return to normal significantly sooner than after an OCTR.

The Agee endoscopic release may therefore be of particular advantage to patients with heavy loading of the palm e.g. heavy laborers and chronic users of crutches who would be seriously disadvantaged if post operative pain and parasthesia should develop. The Agee endoscope is unlikely to cause disruption of the nerve function due to increased carpal pressure during the release.

Whichever technique was employed, the complete resolution of all symptoms is not possible in all patients and this should be explained before release of the flexor retinaculum. This is because Irreversible damage to the median nerve and the sensory corpuscles may well have occurred and would preclude a complete resolution of preoperative symptoms as most of the patients present late after they had experienced the symptoms of median nerve compression.

Conclusions

Surgical treatment by division of the flexor retinaculum gives excellent relief of patients complains. Proper preoperative investigations are important in selecting the surgical procedure

Endoscopic carpal tunnel release is not to be taken lightly It requires a well trained hand surgeon. ECTR results in early return to work, less post operative sensory disturbances. less scar tenderness and cosmetically more acceptable results. When ECTR is contra indicated or can not be done, OCTR still provides a good, safe and effective alternative.

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Case report: Mesenteric panniculitis of transverse colon

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Abstract

Mesenteric panniculitis (MP) of the bowel is very rare. The aim of this paper is to report a case of mesenteric panniculitis of transverse colon.

Keywords: Mesenteric panniculitis, Mesenteric lipodystrophy, Sclerosing mesenteritis

Introduction

Mesenteric panniculitis (MP) is a benign fibro-inflammatory process involving adipose tissue of the mesentery characterized by the presence of fat necrosis, chronic inflammation and fibrosis. It is known by several terms including sclerosing mesenteritis and mesenteric lipodystrophy [1]. It is of an unknown origin. Many consider it as a variant of retroperitoneal fibrosis. It is self-limiting inflammation and seldom causes any serious complications [2].

Discussion

A 60-year-old man presented during March, 2008 with lower abdominal pain started 40 days ago followed by constipation and melaena and associated with nausea, fever, and weight loss. He was hypertensive for the last 10 years and on atenolol 50 mg daily. He had history of sub total thyroidectomy for huge

simple goiter 8 years ago. Physical examination revealed a palpable Para umbilical mass extending to the epigastric region with a normal skin over it. Ultrasound revealed ill defined hyperechoic mass at the para-umbilical area with mild ascitis (Figure-1).

Figure (1): Ultrasound ill defined hyperechoic mass at the para-umbilical area with mild ascitis

Colonoscopy and biopsy showed chronic colitis. MRI showed lower abdominal mass compressing the small bowel with mild ascitis and suspicion of lymphoma (Figure-2).

Barium meal and follow -through showed narrowing of terminal ileum (Figure-3).

Laboratory findings were normal except high E.S.R. 116mm/h

The patient was admitted to hospital with a provisional diagnosis of lymphoma of terminal ileum.

He was prepared for surgery by mechanical bowel preparation, intravenous cefotaxime 1gm and metronidazole 500mg three times daily.

Figure (2): MRI

A laparotomy was performed through a lower mid line incision, there was a little amount of serosanguinous fluid in the peritoneal cavity, the small bowel was normal, the greater omentum and transverse mesocolone were edematous and markedly thickened and the adipose tissue including appendices epiploicae were nodular, the color of the mesentery varied from yellow to red-brown with focal hemorrhages, no enlarged mesenteric lymph nodes were seen. The ascending, transverse and descending colon wall was thickened and edematous as shown in figure-4. Multiple biopsies from the mesentery were taken, tube drain inserted and the wound closed in layers. Post operatively the patient was given intravenous fluid and continued on metronidazole and cefotaxime, he passed motion on the 2nd

post operative day and oral fluid started, the drain discharged about 500 ml of serosanguinous fluid daily and removed on the 5th post operative day.

Figure (3): Barium meal and follow-through showed narrowing of terminal ileum.

Figure (4): The operative findings

The biopsy revealed chronic inflammation of the fatty tissues of the mesentery with fibrosis, so the patient discharged on oral metronidazole 500mg twice daily, cefixime 400mg daily and oral prednisolon 5 mg four times daily for 15 day and tapered in the next 15 day. The patient was seen on August-2008. He was in a good general condition, symptom free, with no palpable abdominal mass, and E.S.R. decreased to 39 mm/h.

Mesenteric panniculitis affects predominantly the mesentery of the small intestine. This process very rarely involves the large intestine [1]. According to Wexner and Attiyeh there have been 122 cases of MP described in the literature and only three involved the mesentery of the colon [3]. The most consistent histological findings were the presence of fibrosis and a chronic inflammatory infiltrate [4].

Macroscopic findings showed enlarged mesentery. Mesenteric involvement may be diffuse nodular or multinodular, with scattered areas of discoloration vary from reddish brown plaques to pale yellow foci. Microscopic findings included anomalous fatty cells with foamy cytoplasm and infiltrations by monocytes, lymphocytes, lipid-laden macrophages and foreign body giant cells. There are areas of fatty necrosis and a variable degree of fibrosis. The fatty necrosis may calcify [5]

The etiology and pathogenesis of the disease are very obscure. Various factors such as blunt abdominal trauma or prior surgery, cold, different drugs, vasculitis, vitamin deficiency, autoimmune processes and allergic disease have been suggested as possible causes [1]. Some of the cases of MP were associated with abdominal tuberculous lymphadenitis [6]. The association of autoimmune hemolytic anemia with MP suggested a possible relationship of an immune mechanism in the pathogenesis of the disease [7].

The clinical manifestation of MP were non specific, abdominal pain is the most common symptom, followed by the presence of a non painful mass or intestinal obstruction [2].

The diagnosis is frequently made by abdominal exploration. A frozen section may be necessary for confirmation of the diagnosis. Only gross macroscopic and

microscopic examination of the surgically removed specimen clarified the diagnosis [1].

Resection (when it is possible) is appropriate intraoperative practise in spite of the benign nature of the disease; this is especially noted in cases of bowel obstruction. [1].

There is no specific treatment for MP. There are reports of response to, antibiotics steroids, immunosuppressive therapy [7, 8].

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Self mutilation in an Iraqi adolescent female

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An Iraqi adolescent female born in 1991 presented with self mutilation. She carved into her flesh with knives when she was upset, used razor blade to cut her skin and, underlying tissue. At the age of three years , she witnessed her father arrest by the ex-regime intelligence because he escaped from the military service to help his family sustain living by working as the salary of the recruited soldier in Iraq during 1995 was less than 2\$ /month).She experienced many family quarrels and mutual verbal and physical abuse by her parents. She was remembering her mother trying to end her life in late 1994. Three months later her father tried to escape out side Iraq, but the military police captured him at the border of Jordon and re-imprisoned and executed him.

Her father had been executed during the rules of the previous regime. The family was left without any financial resources. She was 5 years old. During the year 1997, her mother was forced to marry again (being a second wife) and her father-in-law was alcoholic

The patient described the daily domestic violence as the daily party after drinking. The family decided to leave Iraq to live as refugee in any country .The family arrived Jordan during 1998 and stayed in Jordan for 4 years. She experienced humiliating situation and her mother was forced to work in homes as a domestic

servant at one nigh. The patient was abused sexually by Jordanian citizen aged more than fifty years.

Before the age of 11, her mother decided to return to Iraq whatever the consequences. The patient was trying to forget her physical, mental pain, but in vain. She didn't complete 6 primary school due to the financial difficulties.

At the age of 15 she tried to overcome her insomnia by taking sleeping pills.

Her mother forced her to marry a man over 35 years old, due to the desparate financial status. Marital discord occurred as early as honeymoon period. She was trying to mutilate herself during crises. After any quarrel she used to mutilate her self with a kitchen knife; slicing her arms repeatedly. Sometimes, this teenager heats up an iron just to sear her skin. She lived with her husband and two brothers in her mother's apartment which is less than 60 square meters. The overcrowding was associated with daily quarrels.

The acts of cutting or burning her skin relieved her tension and anxiety, especially after fighting with her husband or getting dumped by a family. Burns and cuts temporarily distracted her from problems and made her feel better. She has now more than 20 separate cuttings in both arms more than 6

cuttings in the legs with a unique self injury near genitalia.

An increasing number of girls cutting, burning or bruising their bodies to help cope with stress has been reported in the literature.

This case demonstrates the complex factors that lead to self mutilation in the Iraqi environment.

Supplement: Cancer in Iraq: 2000-2005

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Content

1-Frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq

2-Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies in Iraq

3-The histopathologic pattern of breast cancer in Iraq

4-The Histopathological pattern lung cancer in Iraq

5-The histopathological pattern of skin cancers in Iraq

Frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Little is known about the frequency of various childhood cancers in Iraq. The aim of this paper is to report the frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq in the largest series of Iraqi patients with cancer.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 5049 cases of cancers occurred in children under 14 years of age accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results: Leukemia is by far the commonest childhood cancer in Iraq accounting for 33% of childhood cancers. The top 10 childhood cancers were : leukemias, Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye (retinoblastomas), soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of testis and ovary.

Conclusion: The pattern of childhood cancer in Iraq is slightly different from the patterns in other countries. Higher frequency of leukemias than most other countries.

Keywords: Childhood, Cancer, Iraq, Pattern

Introduction

Childhood cancers (age at diagnosis: 0-14 years) comprise a variety of malignancies, with incidence varying worldwide by age, sex, ethnicity and geography. Substantial regional differences in the incidence of childhood cancer have been reported. The incidence may vary according to gender, age, race, and ethnicity [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Little is known about childhood cancer in Iraq. The aim of this paper is to describe the pattern of childhood cancer in Iraq. These research findings are useful for prioritizing future childhood cancer research needs. The aim of this paper is to report the frequency of childhood cancers in Iraq in the largest series of Iraqi patients with cancer.

Patients and methods

In largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004) 5049 cases of cancers occurred in children under 14 years of age accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results

Leukemia is by far the commonest childhood cancer in Iraq accounting for 33% of childhood cancers. The top 10 childhood cancers were : leukemias, Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) , central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye (retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of testis and ovary. Cancers of the livers ranked 11th in the list accounting for less than 1% of childhood cancers.

The top 10 childhood cancers in males as shown in table-1 were: leukemias, Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) , central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye (retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of ovary.

	No (%)	Males	Females
Leukemia	1675 (33%)	999	676
NHL	834(16.5%)	537	297
Brain & CNS	786(15.6%)	459	327
Hodgkin lymphoma	262 (5%)	193	69
Kidney	246(4.9%)	135	111
Bone	227(4.5%)	127	100
Eye	173(3.4%)	102	71
Soft tissues	159 (3.1%)	91	68
Adrenal	106 (2.1%)	55	51
Testis/Ovary	90 (1.8%)	26	64
Liver	45 (0.9%)	23	22

Table (1): The pattern of childhood cancers

The top 10 childhood cancers in females as shown in table-1 were : Leukemias, central nervous system neoplasms Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) , central nervous system neoplasms, Non-Hodgkin lymphomas(NHL), renal tumors, bone tumors and Eye

(retinoblastomas),soft tissues tumors, adrenal gland tumors, and tumors of testis and ovary.

Discussion

The frequency of malignant neoplasms in children has been found to vary among countries. For example, in children in Canada, the United States, and Europe, the three most common cancers are leukemias, tumors of the central nervous system (CNST), and lymphomas [7,8,9], whereas in children in Latin America, the order of frequencies is distinct: leukemias are still in first place, with lymphomas being more common than are CNST [8,10,11,12]. In other countries such as Nigeria, Malawi, and Egypt, lymphomas are the principal neoplasias [8].

The percentage of cases of each type of neoplasm in relation to the total number of cancers is also different. In the developed countries, the percentages for leukemias range between 30 and 37%; for CNST, between 18 and 27%; and for lymphomas, between 7 and 12% [7, 8, 9]. In Latin America, the percentages for leukemias are between 27 and 44%; of lymphomas, between 13 and 22%; and of CNST, between 10 and 19% [28, 10, 11, 12]. In African countries, the percentages of lymphomas range between 30 and 64% [8]. In Asian countries such as Japan and China, the percentages of leukemias have been found to be between 30 and 40%; of CNST, between 12 and 20%; and of lymphomas, between 10 and 20% [8].

During the decade 1968-1977 a total of 1488 cases of neoplasms was registered

in Slovakia in children aged 0-14 years .The most common malignancies were leukemias (28.2%), tumors of nervous system (23.9%), lymphomas (14.9%) and Wilm's tumors of kidney (6.7%) [4].

In Poland the most frequent childhood cancers include leukemia, which accounts for (28%) of cancer cases, lymphoma (14.3%) and CNS tumors (16.3%). Neoplasms of the hematopoietic system (leukemias and lymphomas) account for about 42% of all childhood cancers. Malignant lymphomas, bone tumors and germinal tumors are more frequently diagnosed in Poland, but the incidence of central nervous system tumors is lower than in other countries [6].Figure-1 shows the pattern of childhood cancers in 4 countries.

The study of the frequency of cancer in children not only is of interest to the clinical physician because it helps him/her to establish the pre-testing probability for a child suspected of having cancer [13], but also is of interest to the personnel in charge of the planning and programming of the medical attention for these children, as pertains to the assignment of human resources (physicians, specialized nurses, social workers, and others) and to the allotment of financial resources (centers providing medical attention, laboratories, imaging facilities, medicines, etc.) that are necessary for the treatment the children [14].

Conclusion: The pattern of childhood cancer in Iraq is slightly different from the patterns in other countries. Higher frequency of leukemias than most other countries.

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Figure (1): The pattern of childhood countries in 4 countries.

Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies comprise mainly leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma. The annual incidence of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas was reported to be increasing by 3 to 4% in different parts of the developed world during the 1990s, while rates for Hodgkin's disease, myelomas and leukemias were more stable. The aim of this study is to evaluate the pattern of hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies diagnosed by bone marrow examination in the largest series of Iraqi patients with the commoner hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004). There were 10330 cases of the commoner hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies (leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma) accounting for 16% of the total number of Iraqi patients with cancers.

Results: Leukemia was the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. 4476 cases of leukemia were reported; 2618(58.5%) in males and 1858 (41.5%) in females. 1502 cases of Hodgkin disease were registered

accounting for all cancer cases. 925(61.6%) in males and 577(38.4%) in females. There were 3883 cases of NHL accounting for 6% of all cancers. There were 469 cases of multiple lymphomas accounting for 0.73% of all cancers.

Conclusion: In contrast to many western countries, in Iraq the incidence rate of Leukemias is increasing while trends for the other hematolymphopoietic malignancies are strikingly stable.

Keywords: Hemopoietic, lymphoreticular, malignancies.

Introduction

Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies are derived from cells of bone marrow and lymphoreticular system comprising mainly leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma. In addition to the less common conditions such as polycythemia vera, mastocytosis, and malignant histiocytosis. Polycythemia vera is a myeloproliferative, not strictly speaking a neoplastic disorder, but it's commonly included in this category. The incidence of these malignancies is very important because many of them can be cured by modern therapies. The annual incidence of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas was reported to be increasing by 3 to 4% in different parts of the developed world during the 1990s, while the rates of Hodgkin's disease, myelomas and leukemias were more stable. Excesses of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas have been observed in populations exposed to

phenoxy-acetic-acid herbicides, to insecticides and to organic solvents [1, 2].

There is lack of information about the relative prevalence and annual incidence of leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma in Iraq. The aim of this study is to evaluate the pattern of the commoner forms of hemopoetic and lymphoreticular malignancies diagnosed by bone marrow examination in the largest series of Iraq patients with these disorders.

Patients and methods

In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004). There were 10330 cases of the commoner hemopoetic and lymphoreticular malignancies (leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma) accounting for 16% of the total number of Iraqi patients with cancers.

Results

Leukemias are heterogeneous malignant neoplasms of leucopoetic cells and are generally classified according to the cell type which predominates.

Leukemias were the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. 4476 cases of leukemia were reported; 2618(58.5%) in males and 1858 (41.5%) in females. Acute lymphoblastic leukemia was the commonest histopathology accounting for 41.5% of all cases. Acute

myeloid leukemia was the second most common histopathology accounting for 20.5%. Chronic Myeloid leukemia was the third most common histopathology accounting for 11.4%. Table-1 shows the frequency of various leukemias histopathology.

Histopathology	
Acute lymphoblastic	1856(41.5%)
Acute myeloid	917 (20.5%)
Chronic Myeloid	509 (11.4%)
Chronic lymphoid	302
Myeloid	50
Hairy cell	29
Lymphoid	15
Acute monocytic	15
Acute promyelocytic	12
Eosinophilic	3
Erythroleukemia	3
Acute myelomonocytic	2
Mast cell	2
Adult T-cell leukemia/lymphoma	2
Subacute Myeloid	2
Lymphosarcoma cell	2
Basophilic	2

Table (1): The frequency of various leukemias histopathology.

1502 cases of Hodgkin disease were registered accounting for of all cancer cases. 925(61.6%) in males and 577(38.4%) in females .There were 3883 cases of NHL accounting for 6% of all cancers. There were 469 cases of multiple lymphomas accounting for 0.73% of all cancers. Table-1 shows the number of registered cases of the commoner hemopoetic malignancies each year.

Year	Leukemia			Hodgkin's disease			NHL			MM		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
2000	375	304	679	175	118	293	403	270	673	33	31	64
2001	474	316	790	207	118	325	474	316	790	47	29	76
2002	491	301	792	192	140	332	514	315	829	75	59	134
2003	482	341	823	173	119	292	413	265	678	41	38	79
2004	796	596	1392	178	82	260	539	374	913	72	44	116
			4476			1502			3883			469

Table (1): The number of registered cases of the commoner hemopoietic malignancies each year

Discussion

The incidence rate of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas (NHL) is increasing in most Western countries, while trends for the other hematolymphopoietic malignancies are strikingly stable. Excesses of non-Hodgkin's Lymphomas have been observed in populations exposed to phenoxy-acetic acid herbicides, to insecticides and to organic solvents. Some of these exposures, in particular TCDD, which is a contaminant of phenoxy herbicides, DDT and chlorinated solvents, have been reported to alter cell-mediated immunity. The incidence of NHL is also increased among subjects with HIV infection and subjects undergoing heart or kidney transplantation, all of whom experience immunodeficiency. A hypothesis that has been put forward recently is that the NHL increase is related to increased exposure to sunlight, which has immunosuppressive effects. From a mechanistic point of view, one can hypothesize that NHL is caused by exposures that induce proliferation and immortalization of B-cells, followed by T-cell impairment entailing cell-mediated immune deficiency [10, 11, 12, 13].

In contrast to many western countries where the incidence rate of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas (NHL) is increasing, while trends for the other hematolymphopoietic are strikingly stable, in Iraq the incidence rate of Leukemias is increasing while trends for the other hematolymphopoietic malignancies are strikingly stable.

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The histopathologic pattern of breast cancer in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Breast Cancer is the most frequent cancer in women worldwide .It is important to understand the histological pattern because histology as a prognostic factor has been well documented. No data is available about the histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq.

The aim of this paper is to report the histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq in the in the largest series of Iraqi patients with types of newly diagnosed cancers.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 10277 cases of breast cancer, 464 males (4.5%), and 9813 females (95.5%) occurred in accounting for approximately 16 % of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results: The histomorphological types seen among breast cancers indicated that there were 7876 cases (76.6%) with histology of Infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC) not otherwise specified (NOS), which was found to be the most common type. This was followed in decreasing order by infiltrating lobular carcinoma in 562 cases (5.46 %); adenocarcinoma carcinoma in 558 cases (5.43%)

Conclusion: The histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq differs from the previously reported pattern in Asian and African countries such as India and Nigeria.

Keywords: Breast, Cancer, Iraq

Introduction

Breast Cancer is the most frequent cancer in women worldwide with 1.05 million new cases every year and represents over 20% of all malignancies among females [1]. Over 50% of breast cancer incidence occurs in the developed world. High-risk areas include Europe and North America. The lowest rates are reported from Africa and Asia. However, it still ranks as the commonest cancer among women in these regions. Incidence of breast cancer is increasing in most countries, including the areas, which have had previously low rates [2-4]. It is estimated that in 2001 there were approximately 80,000 new breast

The aim of this paper is to report the histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq in the in largest series of Iraqi patients with types of newly diagnosed cancers.

Patients and methods

In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 10277 cases of breast cancer, 464 males, and (4.5%), 9813 females (95.5%) occurred in accounting for approximately % of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results

In the present study, various morphological variants and patterns were observed. The histomorphological types seen among breast cancers indicated that there were 7876 cases (76.6%) with histology of Infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC) not otherwise specified (NOS), which was found to be the most common type. This was followed in decreasing order by infiltrating lobular carcinoma in 562 cases (5.46 %); adenocarcinoma carcinoma in 558 cases (5.43%), epithelial 145 in cases (1.4%), medullary carcinoma 114 in cases (1.1%), Comedo carcinoma 67 (0.65%) (Table 1).

Discussion

Breast cancer incidence rates are increasing worldwide. In Iraq, it is the most common cancer accounting for 16% of all cancers in Iraqi patients. The continuing rise in breast cancer incidence has created an urgent need to develop strategies for prevention.

Few studies of international variation in breast cancer have considered tumor histology.

It is important to understand the relationship of histological type to etiology, and to allow separation of entities with distinct etiologies. Histology as a prognostic factor has been well documented. Patients with histology of Infiltrating duct carcinoma (IDC) (NOS) have a poor survival compared to other types [4, 5]. In the present study among the different histomorphological types, Infiltrating duct Carcinoma (NOS) was found to be the most common type occurring in cases (76.6%).

Histomorphological type	No. %
Infiltrating duct carcinoma.	7876(76.6%)
Infiltrating lobular carcinoma	562 (5.46%)
Adenocarcinoma	558 (5.43%)
Epithelial	145 (1.4%)
Medullary carcinoma	114 (1.1%)
Comedo carcinoma	67 (0.65%)
Phyllodes tumor	50 (0.48%)
Mixed ductal & lobular	48 (0.46%)
Infiltrating ductular	35 (0.34%)
Paget's disease	34 (0.33%)
Mucinous adenocarcinoma	24

Table 1: Distribution of cases according to histomorphological types

The histopathological cancer pattern of breast cancer in Iraq differs from the previously reported pattern in Asian and African countries such as India and Nigeria.

The commonest histological types of breast cancer in Nigerian women in a study conducted over a twelve-year period (January 1993-December 2004) were IDC (not otherwise specified) constituted the majority of breast cancer accounting for 75.5% while papillary carcinoma was the least common (2.7%). Ductal carcinoma in situ accounted for 6.6%.

In India the histomorphological types seen among 569 female breast cancers indicated that there were 502 cases (88.2%) with histology of IDC not otherwise specified (NOS), which was found to be the most common type. This was followed in decreasing order by infiltrating lobular carcinoma in 21 cases (3.7%); colloid carcinoma in 6 cases (1.1%), ductal carcinoma-in-situ in 6 cases (1.1%), metaplastic type in 5 cases (0.9%), schirrous carcinoma in 5 cases (0.9%), apocrine type in 4 cases (0.7%)

and the rest 20 cases (3.5%) with other types of carcinoma [7].

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The Histopathological pattern of lung cancer in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Geographical differences have been observed in the incidence of various histological patterns of lung cancer. Shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence in the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries.

No information is available about the frequency of various histological types of lung cancer in Iraqi patients. The aim of this study is to describe the histopathologic pattern of lung cancer in the largest series of Iraqi patients with lung cancer.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 5157 cases of lung cancers (4105 males, 1052 females) occurred in accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males.

Results: The four commonest histopathological types of lung cancer are Squamous cell carcinoma accounting for 37.6% of the cases, adenocarcinoma accounting for 13% of the cases small cell carcinoma accounting for 8.3% of the cases

, and large cell carcinoma accounting for 7% of the cases.

Conclusion: The shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence in the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries were not observed in this large sample of Iraqi patients with lung cancer registered during five year period.

Keywords: Lung, Cancer, Iraq, Histopathological types.

Introduction

Primary lung cancer is essentially carcinoma of the bronchus. Occasionally cancer occurs in the trachea and pleura. Lung cancer is the leading cause (28%) of cancer deaths worldwide [1, 2] and accounted for 163,500 new cases of cancer in the United States in 2004 [2]. Compared with the other major cancers, breast, colorectal, and prostate has witnessed only modest improvements in its survival rates and clinical outcome up to the present time, and is the only major cancer type to have increased in the number of deaths annually [2, 3].

Histopathologic heterogeneity is a major confounding factor in lung cancer diagnosis and treatment [4]. Classically, lung cancer comprises three primary histological subtypes: carcinoid, small cell, and non-small cell, which account for about 2%, 13%, and 86% of lung

cancers, respectively. Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is further subdivided into at least three histologic subtypes: adenocarcinoma (AD), squamous cell carcinoma (SQ)/epidermoid and large cell carcinoma. Small cell lung cancer (SCLC) is the most aggressive form of lung cancer, includes small cell carcinoma, mixed small cell/large cell carcinoma, and combined small cell carcinoma. Carcinoids (COIDs) form a distinct histologic tumor subtype that may secrete bioactive molecules, and are further subdivided into typical and atypical varieties [5]. Tumors such as adenosquamous and neuroendocrine carcinomas possess histological characteristics of more than one subtype, whereas tumors from the same histopathologic subtype may have dissimilar clinical outcomes such as drug response [6, 7].

No information is available about the frequency of various histological types of lung cancer in Iraqi patients. The aim of this study is to describe the histopathologic pattern of lung cancer in the largest series of Iraqi patients with lung cancer.

Patients and methods

In largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004), 5157 cases of lung cancers (4105 males, 1052 females) occurred accounting for approximately 8% of all cancer cases in Iraq. Lungs and the bronchi were the second most common site of cancer and the first most common site in males.

Results

The commonest histopathological types of lung cancer as shown in table-1 are Squamous cell carcinoma accounting for 37.6% of the cases, adenocarcinoma accounting for 13% of the cases small cell carcinoma accounting for 8.3% of the cases, and large cell carcinoma accounting for 7 % of the cases. In addition there were 29 cases of tracheal cancer, histopathology is shown in table-2. For every 178 cases of lung cancer there were one case of tracheal cancer. In addition there were 31 cases of pleural cancer mesothelioma.

Histopathology	No (%)
Squamous cell carcinoma	1940 (37.6%)
Adenocarcinoma	672 (13 %)
Small cell carcinoma	428 (8.3%)
large cell carcinoma	361 (7%)
Epithelial tumor	240 (4.65%)
Oat cell carcinoma	130 (2.5%)
Carcinoma, undifferentiated	89 (1.7%)
Carcinoid tumor	19 (0.36%)
Carcinoma, Anaplastic	15 (0.3%)

Table (1): The commonest histopathological types of lung cancer in Iraqi patients.

Histopathology	No
Squamous cell carcinoma	19
Small cell carcinoma	4
Adenocarcinoma	3
large cell carcinoma	1
Carcinoma, undifferentiated	1
Squamous –small cell carcinoma	1

Table (2): The histopathological types of tracheal cancer in Iraqi patients.

Discussion

Geographical differences have been observed in the incidence of various histological pattern of lung cancer. Shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence during

the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries.

In Europe, the squamous cell type still predominates and an increase in incidence of adenocarcinoma has only been reported in the Netherlands. In Asia, in the 1960s and 1970s, the proportion of adenocarcinoma was higher than in North America or Europe and seems to be increasing [8].

In Varse lung cancer incidence rates in the period 1976-1992 overall, lung cancer had stopped increasing in males since the late 1980s, and had started declining in middle-aged men. Conversely, upward trends persisted in females up to 1991-1992. Although it decreased from 13 to 9, the male-to-female incidence ratio was, in 1991-1992 still substantially higher than in the U.S. and North Europe. Specific trends emerged according to histological type(s), with declines (males) or stabilization (females) for squamous-cell carcinoma and gradual increases for small-cell carcinoma in males. Adenocarcinoma was the only lung cancer type whose incidence rates increased similarly (2.5-fold) in males and females thus approaching, in 1991-1992, in the two sexes combined, the rate for squamous-cell carcinoma [9].

In Iraqi patients with lung cancer the changes in the incidence of squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma during a five year-period were very similar. Figure-1 shows the number of the registered cases of both histological types during five year period.

Figure (1): The number of the registered cases of both histological types during five year period.

Conclusion: The shifts in histological tumor type distribution, chiefly an increase in adenocarcinoma, have been reported to accompany changes in lung cancer incidence in the last two decades in the United States and several other developed countries were not observed in this large sample of Iraqi patients with lung cancer registered over a five year period.

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The histopathological pattern of skin cancers in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Skin cancers comprise a variety of malignancies, with varying incidence of the histopathological types worldwide. Little is known about skin cancers in Iraq. Population-based figures on skin cancers are essential for a realistic assessment of the disease burden, prevention modes and the need for caring. The aim of this paper is to present the first and the largest study of the histopathological types of skin cancers in Iraq.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancers registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004) 2585 cases of skin cancers occurred in all age groups accounting for approximately 4% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results: The top skin cancers in Iraq were Basal cell carcinoma (BCC), Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), melanoma, Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma. BCC is the commonest skin cancer in Iraq. There were 1111 cases of BCC accounting for 43% of all skin cancers. SCC is second most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 904 cases of SCC accounting for 35% of all skin cancers. Melanoma is third most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 160 cases of melanoma accounting for only 6% of all skin cancers.

Conclusion: The top skin cancers in Iraq were BCC, SCC, melanoma, Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma.

Keywords: Skin cancer-Frequency-Iraq

Introduction

Skin cancers comprise a variety of malignancies, with varying incidence of histopathological types worldwide. Little is known about skin cancer in Iraq. The incidence of skin cancers Melanoma and nonmelanoma skin cancer (NMSCs) has been reported to be rapidly increasing in some parts of the world [1, 2, 3, 4]. Population-based figures on skin cancer are essential for a realistic assessment of the disease burden, prevention modes and the need for caring. The aim of this paper is to present the first and the largest study of the histopathological types of skin cancer in Iraq.

Patients and methods

In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004) 2585 cases of skin cancers occurred in all age groups accounting for approximately 4% of all cancer cases in Iraq.

Results

A total of 2425 non-melanoma skin cancers were registered in all age groups; 1342 cases occurred in males and 1083 cases occurred in females. 17 cases occurred in children under 5 years of age. The average annual incidence of non-melanoma skin cancers 2.20 /100.000 population. A total of 160 of melanoma were registered in patients between the ages of 20 to 75 years; 84 cases in males occurred and 76 occurred in females. The average annual incidence of melanoma was 0.14 /100.000 population. There were 8 cases of nodular melanoma, and one case of Amelanotic melanoma.

The top skin cancers in Iraq were Basal cell carcinoma (BCC), Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), melanoma, Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma. BCC is the commonest skin cancer in Iraq. There were 1111 cases of BCC accounting for (43%) of all skin cancers. SCC is second most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 904 cases of SCC accounting for (35%) of all skin cancers. Melanoma is third most common skin cancer in Iraq. There were 160 cases of melanoma accounting for only (6%) of all skin cancers. Table-1 shows the percentage of various histopathologies of skin cancers. Three cancers BCC, SCC, and melanoma accounted for more than 80% of all histopathologic types as shown in figure-1.

Discussion

The incidence of skin cancers Melanoma and nonmelanoma skin cancer (NMSCs) has been reported to be rapidly increasing in some parts of the world [1, 2, 3, 4].

Histopathology	No (%)
BCC	1111(43%)
SCC	904 (35%)
Melanoma	160 (6%)
Dermatofibrosarcoma	52 (2%)
Basosquamous carcinoma	48 (1.85%)
Kaposi sarcoma	48 (1.85%)
SCS Ker type	29 (1.1%)
Epithelial tumor	24 (0.9%)
Adenocarcinoma	17 (0.66%)
Fibrous Histocytoma	12 (0.46%)
liposarcoma	8 [4 Myxoid]
Sebaceous Adenocarcinoma	6
Bowens disease	3
Eccrine Acrospiroma	2

Table (1):The percentage of various histopathologies of skin cancers.

Figure (1): Three cancers BCC, SCC, and melanoma accounted for more than 80% of all histopathologic types

The rising incidence rates of NMSC are probably caused by a combination of increased sun exposure or exposure to ultraviolet (UV) light, increased outdoor activities, changes in clothing style, increased longevity, ozone depletion, genetics and in some cases, immune

suppression. The frequency of its occurrence is closely associated with the constitutive color of the skin and depends on the geographical zone. The highest incidence rates have been reported from Queensland, Australia with 56 new cases per year per 100,000 for men and 43 for women [3, 4]. The Robert Koch Institute in Germany estimates the incidence of melanoma skin cancer as 7 cases in 100 000 person Between 1998 and 2001, Katalinic A et al reported the registration of 1784 malignant melanoma with an estimated incidence rates of 12.3 and 14.8 in 100 000 men and women.[1]. Obviously the incidence of (NMSCs) in Iraq was lower despite it's a region with high ultraviolet light exposure

Conclusion: The top skin cancers in Iraq were BCC, SCC, melanoma,

Dermatofibrosarcoma, Basosquamous carcinoma, Kaposi sarcoma.

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